

D4.1

Open Labs design and integration and validation methodology

MultiX

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Abstract

This document presents a comprehensive validation and integration methodology designed to ensure the realization of the MultiX technologies using vertical oriented Proof of Concepts (PoCs). The document provides an overall description of the methodology to be used during the project execution, focusing on the roadmap and phases envisioned during the project, and the mechanisms established to monitor the progress of the integration and validation activities, and at the same time assess the completeness of the targeted tests. This document also describes the MultiX Open Labs environments, detailing the available and targeted technologies to be used during the validation activities, and the mechanisms to access the testbeds to deploy software components. Finally, this document provides an initial set of experiments and demonstrations envisioned during the project execution providing details regarding the MultiX sensing technologies to be validated and the targeted KPIs.

Keywords

Validation, methodology, open labs

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Acronyms and definitions (Modify)

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AD/DA	Analog-to-Digital and Digital-to-Analog
AGV	Autonomous Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ANEC	European Association for the Coordination of Consumer Representation in Standardisation
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AP	Access Point
BBU	Baseband Unit
BLER	Block Error Rate
BPSK	Binary Phase-Shift Keying
BTS	Base Station Transceiver
CFAR	Constant False Alarm Rate
CIR	Channel Impulse Response
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CNC	Computer Numerical Controlled
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CPRI	Common Public Radio Interface
CSI	Channel State Information
CSI-RS	Channel State Information Reference Signals

DASH	Data Access and Security Hub
DMP	Data Management Plan
DNN	Data Network Name
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DSP	Digital Signal Processing
E2E	End-to-End
EA	Ethics Advisor
eCPRI	Enhanced Common Public Radio Interface
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EMF	Electromagnetic Field
ESR	Ethics Evaluation Summary Report
ESPRIT	Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Technique
EU	European Union
FRA	EU Agency for Fundamental Rights
FFT	Fast Fourier Transform
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
FTM	Fine Time Measurements
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System

GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
ID	Identity Document
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
IEEE	Institute for Electric Electronic Engineers
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
ISM	Industrial, Scientific and Medical
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ISM	Industrial, Scientific and Medical
IQ	In-Phase (I) and Quadrature (Q)
IR	Infrared
LO	Local Oscillator
MAC	Medium Access Control
MAG	Multistakeholder Advisory Group
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple-Input Multiple-Output
ML	Machine Learning
ML-DT	Multi-Layer Digital Twin
mmWave	Millimetre Wave
MoCAP	Motion Capture
MOCN	Multi-Operator Core Network
MoG	Mixture of Gaussian

MP6RC	MP6R Controller
MPS	MultiX Perception System
MUSIC	MUltiple Signal Classification
MP6R	MultiX Perceptive 6G-RAN
MX-PDK	Multi-x platform development kit
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-Standalone
OAI	OpenAirInterface
OFDM	Orthogonal Frequency-Division Multiplexing
OTFS	Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS)
P2P	Point-to-Point
PHY	Physical Layer
PoC	Proof of Concept
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technologies
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
RF	Radio Frequency
RFSoc	Radio Frequency System-on-Chip
RT	Real Time
RU	Radio Unit
SA	Standalone

SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDR	Software Defined Radio
SoC	System-on-Chip
SMA	SubMiniature version A
SNR	Signal-to-noise ratio
SSB	Synchronization Signal Blocks
STC	Siemens Technology Center
ToF	Time of Flight
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UHD	USRP Hardware Driver
UK	United Kingdom
ULA	Uniform Linear Array
UPA	Uniform Planar Array
UPF	User Plane Function
USRP	Universal Software Radio Peripheral
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Network
WP	Work Package
WR	White Rabbit

Table of partners

Short Name	Partner
UC3M	Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
APP	Apple Technology Engineering BV&CO KG
OTE	ORGANISMOS TILEPIKOINONION TIS ELLADOS OTE AE
INT	Intel Deutschland GmbH
IDE	InterDigital Europe LTD
NEC	NEC Laboratories Europe GmbH
NEC Italia	NEC Italia S.p.A.
SAG	Siemens AG
TSA	Telefónica S.A.
BR	BubbleRAN
NXW	Nextworks
CNIT	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Telecomunicazioni
I2CAT	Fundació Privada i2CAT, Internet i Innovació digital a Catalunya
IMDEA	Fundación IMDEA Networks
IHP	IHP GmbH - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics
IASA	Institute of Accelerating Systems and Applications
KUL	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven
UC	Universidad de Cantabria

1 Executive summary

This document presents a comprehensive overview of the experimental, integration, and validation framework established to support the validation and demonstration activities of the MultiX project. It defines the methodological foundation, testbed infrastructure, and Proof of Concept (PoC) strategy that collectively enable the realization and evaluation of the technological innovations of the project.

The integration and validation methodology establishes the base approach for the integration of the MultiX software components into the test environments for the realization of the project PoCs. It defines a flexible methodology to enable the consistent description of the targeted experiments to be ran in the context of the PoCs. Moreover, it describes the mechanisms to track the progress of the activities and results. The methodology also establishes mechanisms to integrate software components into the MultiX Open Labs and lays out a roadmap considering the software deliveries of the project and the related milestones.

The MultiX Open Labs and testing facilities form the core of the experimental infrastructure of the project. These testbeds host the MultiX Perception System (MPS), which introduces multi-layered sensing capabilities into the Radio Access Network (RAN) to realize Integrated Sensing and Communication (ISAC), and the MP6R Controller (MP6RC), which extends RAN control functions to coordinate multi-technology integration across 3GPP, non-3GPP and external sensing domains. Together, these facilities provide a robust and flexible environment for validating and demonstrating the functionalities and results of the project with the MultiX Data Access and Security Hub (DASH) related developments.

The MultiX PoCs aim at showcasing the introduced innovations through targeted experiments in vertical-oriented scenarios. The PoC experiment presented in this document defined a target scenario, high-level procedures, and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), ensuring alignment with the set technical goals of the project and demonstrating the practical impact of MultiX technologies across relevant vertical use cases. This includes the validation of the: (i) Multi-static, multi-technology and multi-band innovations; (ii) Enhanced sensor fusion technologies and developments; (iii) System level developments for the automated configuration and exposure of sensing results; and (iv) the collection and usage of industrial environment, human presence, human positioning and vital sign estimation information in vertical use case scenarios.

2 Introduction

The present document aims to provide a comprehensive description of the experimental and methodological framework established to support MultiX validation and demonstration activities. It serves three main purposes: (i) describe in detail the testbeds comprising the MultiX Open Labs and other infrastructure that will be employed during the PoC validation activities, with particular emphasis on their Radio Access Technologies (RATs), sensing capabilities, and MultiX targeted infrastructure innovations; (ii) to outline the validation and integration methodology that will ensure the effective incorporation of the developed software components into the testbeds, thereby enabling the realization of the PoCs and experiments targeted during the project; and (iii) to refine and enhance the definition of the PoCs, consolidating the definition of the initial set of experiments their scope, objectives, and expected impact.

The MultiX Open Labs testbeds are the core experimental environments within which the project's technical solutions will be evaluated, and where the MultiX innovations shall be deployed for future research activities. In particular, these testbeds provide: (i) the MPS, which incorporates three levels of sensing functions into the RAN stack to realize ISAC across heterogeneous sensors and technologies. Moreover; (ii) the MP6RC, which enhances the RAN control plane to manage and coordinate multi-technology integration, encompassing both 3GPP and non-3GPP systems, as well as external sensing modalities such as radar, LiDAR, and cameras. The testbeds ensure that the developed components can be validated using state-of-the-art technologies.

In addition, this deliverable defines a systematic validation and integration methodology. This methodology addresses the initial high-level plan including processes, interfaces, and tools required to seamlessly integrate the software modules of the project into the selected testbeds. Moreover, the methodology provides initial guidelines for the realization of experiments and production of reproducible experiments. The methodology also serves as a blueprint for iterative refinement, enabling feedback-driven improvements during the course of the integration and testing activities.

Finally, the document provides an enhanced definition of the PoCs. This refinement involves a clearer definition of: (i) Envisioned experiment procedures; (ii) Improved mapping to MultiX technologies and innovations; (iii) KPIs associated to the sensing and to the service; and (iv) validation criteria, and demonstration value. The enhanced PoC definitions not only serve to align the technical developments but also provide practical examples of the usage of the MultiX technologies in vertical oriented use cases.

3 Integration and validation methodology

3.1 Validation methodology

The validation methodology is structured around the definition and use of experiment templates. These templates provide a concise and unified summary that describe how PoC validation activities are designed, executed, and assessed and ensure consistency. There are two phases focusing on ensuring a perfect alignment between prototypes and effective testing and validation of the project goals.

3.1.1 Validation phases

The validation plan can be divided into different phases as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 MultiX validation phases

Phase 1: preparation and planning

The initial phase of the prototype development process is devoted to identifying the different experiments through which the PoC is evaluated. Then, a concrete PoC development plan is defined, splitting the experiment of the PoC into a subset of tests and activities. The PoC validation plan can be updated in subsequent phases if needed to incorporate enhancements or refinements required on tests. Table 1 presents a template to be used for capturing experimental information per PoC.

Phase 2: integration and validation

Once the preparation phase is complete, each iteration of the test is performed to ensure that the expected experiment to be evaluated in the next phase is ready. The set of identified experiments to validate may be enhanced during the process including additional validation tests.

More details regarding the integration methodology are provided in section 3.2, in particular, Table 2, which captures the information required for the test and integration phase for PoC 1 and PoC 2.

Phase 3: Report, analysis and recommendations

The experiments generate a report document structured to communicate the findings clearly, thereby facilitating their comprehension and reproducibility with the following structure:

- **Title and summary of the test:** A concise title with a brief description of the test that will be reported and highlighting the main findings.
- **Objectives:** State the main purpose of the test, KPIs identified and expected outcomes.
- **Results and Analysis:** Include a description of the obtained results and their implications in the MultiX architecture, including comparisons with the selected baseline if applicable.

The information in the final report might differ from the initial test object definitions because details can be refined during the test itself. The report will note these modifications or refinements, acting as a monitoring record for the entire process.

3.1.2 Experiment templates

Experiment templates provide a structured way to design, document, and execute experiments within testbeds, ensuring consistency and reproducibility across different research efforts. They capture the essential elements of an experiment, such as its objectives, required components, technologies and services, and the overall workflow to be applied. By standardizing this information, experiment templates make it easier for researchers and developers to replicate scenarios, compare results, and build upon prior work, ultimately fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing.

Beyond documentation, experiment templates also act as a practical tool for tracking and monitoring the execution of experiments. They can define dependencies between different components, specify performance metrics to be monitored, and outline the sequence of actions required for execution. This structured representation reduces the risk of errors, facilitates automation, and allows for scalability when conducting multiple or complex experiments. In doing so, experiment templates bridge the gap between conceptual research ideas and their concrete implementation in testbeds, ensuring experiments are both transparent and repeatable.

Table 1 Experiment template

Item	Description
ID	<i>Human readable identifier used for internal reference (e.g. PoC1-<x>)</i>
Name	<i>Human readable name of the Experiment</i>
Description	<i>Short description of the experiment</i>

DASH Services	<i>Summary from Dash services targeted</i>
MPS Technologies	<i>Summary from MultiX related tests</i>
Targeted sensing / perception metrics	<i>Summary of metrics results</i>
MultiX Innovations	<i>Reference to MultiX innovations</i>
Targeted KPIs	<i>Reference to KPIs to be addressed by the experiment/test</i>
Related Tests	<i>List of tests (to be provided when final list of tests is specified)</i>
Targeted TRL	<i>Expected TRLs associated to each test</i>

3.2 Integration methodology

The proposed integration methodology is built around the definition and use of test templates as the primary artifacts to guide, validate, and demonstrate the integration of the outcomes of the project. These templates act as blueprint, ensuring that all relevant aspects of the integration process are consistently captured, harmonized, and evaluated. In comparison to experiment templates, a test template offers a more fine-grained definition, detailing the specific procedures, parameters, and conditions under which the components or systems are validated. Tests are narrower in scope, focusing on precise aspects such as functionality, performance under specific loads, or compliance with technical requirements.

3.2.1 Test templates

As shown in Table 2 the test templates document the MP6R technologies to be integrated, including the multi-sensor, multi-band, and multi-technology innovations and the DASH targeted services. This provides a transparent view of the technical integration aspects, ensuring that integration paths are traceable and that potential issues are identified early. The definition of the templates to be executed will be provided in the D4.2 and D4.3 deliverables.

The templates define the high-level workflows supported by the integrated components and technologies, providing insights regarding data flows and process steps. These workflows represent an implementation and a scenario-specific subset of the generic architectural workflows of the MultiX architecture to enable the verification. The specific validation mechanism is also included and described in the test template to ensure an aligned vision upon the success criteria. The tests are also expected to be used to collect KPIs associated to the PoC or the specific technology, which shall contribute to the overall project validation activities. Therefore, the test templates include a specific field to determine the KPIs targeted to be collected during the test execution. Validation strategies and metrics are included in the templates, specifying how outcomes will be tested and what determines a successful integration.

Table 2 Test template

Item	Description
ID	<i>Human readable identifier used for internal reference (e.g. PoC1-<x>-<y>)</i>
Name	<i>A human readable name for the experiment</i>
Description	<i>Description of the targeted experiment</i>
DASH Services	<i>DASH services demonstrated</i>
MPS Technologies	<i>MPS technologies demonstrated during the test</i>
MultiX infrastructure facility	<i>Reference to infrastructure description</i>
High-level test diagram	<i>Diagram indicating control and data plane elements, sensors, etc.</i>
Targeted sensing / perception metrics	<i>List of the metrics used during the experiment</i>
MultiX Innovations	<i>Reference to the MultiX innovations</i>
Targeted KPIs/KVIs	<i>Reference to KPIs linked to the use cases associated with the PoCs</i>
Related Tests	<i>List of tests</i>
Targeted TRL	<i>Expected TRLs associated to each test</i>

3.2.2 Execution and reporting

The execution of the integration test is coordinated among the different partners involved in the test, and the outcome will be reported in live documents that capture the successful validation of the test, identified problems and the results in terms of KPIs.

These live documents will be used to provide feedback to the architectural and development activities in the WP2 and WP3, and will be used to track the integration activities that have been performed. Use of bug tracking mechanisms will be analysed together with WP2 and WP3.

3.3 MultiX Open labs

The MultiX Open labs play a crucial role in the integration and validation, providing an environment where the different technological components developed within the project may be brought together and tested in a cohesive system. This includes the integration of the MP6R system, which combines multi-sensor, multi-band, and multi-technology elements, enabling the execution of system-level tests and experiments. Moreover, the MultiX Open labs will be used for future exploitation activities of the project results.

3.3.1 Deployment of software components

The deployment of software components in the testbeds is mainly supported through secure VPN access, enabling software developers and maintainers to connect remotely to the environments. The testbeds provide computing infrastructure, offering resources for the deployment, execution, and validation of software components using the technologies available in the testbed. To ensure coordination and transparency, a live document is maintained to track targeted deployments, allowing for monitoring progress, updating status, and documenting any issues or adjustments.

3.3.2 Integration of sensing technologies and RATs

The integration of technologies and infrastructures is coordinated through a live document that tracks targeted integration, required support, and associated activities. This document serves as a single point of reference for all the partners and particularly the testbed representatives, capturing integration objectives, timelines, technical requirements, and resource needs while ensuring alignment across teams. This enables visibility and alignment of the progress and responsibilities, it facilitates effective collaboration, identifies potential risks early, and promotes accountability.

3.4 High-level integration and validation roadmap

In Figure 2 we represent the envisioned timeline for the integration and validation activities, considering the established roadmap of the project for software deliveries and milestones. This deliverable concludes the methodology definition phase. As depicted in the figure the next phase will be dedicated to the preparation of the software repositories and the preparation of the testbed for the initial integration activities. The integration activities will start on M12, focusing on the integration of the initial sensing enablers developed in WP3. The second phase of the integration activities target the integration of the system components developed in WP2. All these integration results shall be included and reported in D2.2. The final validation includes the realization of the all tests and activities related to the experiments used for the validation of the PoCs. Moreover, this final validation phase includes the realization of the public demonstrations and the establishment of the lessons learnt.

[D4.1] – Open Labs design and integration and validation methodology

Figure 2 MultiX integration and validation roadmap

4 MultiX Open Labs and testing facilities

This section discusses the MultiX open labs and other testing facilities, particularly focusing on describing the MultiX sensing technologies that will be developed and made available on each facility, the computing capabilities to deploy MultiX software developments and the mechanisms to access the computing infrastructure for the software deployment. The focus is set on the description of the MultiX Open Labs, which are the main reference for the validation activities of the project, but this deliverable also documents other infrastructure facilities that will be used during the PoC experimentation activities.

4.1 Madrid Open Lab

4.1.1 5TONIC

Overview of Experimental Infrastructure

5TONIC is a research and development laboratory whose principal aim is to facilitate the design, prototyping and testing of novel technologies to expedite their adoption in production 5G and beyond networks. To this end, it employs a vendor-neutral environment where both industry and academic partners can collaborate seamlessly to develop solutions across myriad verticals including transportation, manufacturing, healthcare, energy, and emergency services.

Testbed

The core strengths of 5TONIC enable it to serve as a research and testing base for wireless sensing. The complete 5G architecture of the platform connects RAN and core components with programmable transport, Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and SDN/NFV platforms and AI/Machine Learning (ML) services, which form fundamental elements for real-time sensing and data processing. The platform enables various RATs such as 5G NR (NSA and SA), Wi-Fi 6/6E/7, LTE and NB-IoT, as it enables diverse signal sources and deployment scenarios for sensing applications. 5TONIC provides a flexible testing space that integrates commercial equipment (e.g., Ericsson) with open-source platforms like OpenAirInterface (OAI), Amarisoft, and srsRAN to enable fast development and evaluation of new sensing algorithms. The laboratory setup is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: MultiX Open Lab 5TONIC Lab setup.

The platform connects edge and core networks by using Open5GS/OAI5GC-based cores along with containerized VNFs and virtualized infrastructure through Kubernetes and OpenStack, which allow efficient distribution of sensing workloads. This setup enables the deployment of DASH Network functions, such as data transformation, processing, storage and exposure, in a distributed and virtualized environment, allowing easy scalability and customization of functionalities. The combination of remote access through VPN-secured connections and automation tools with CI/CD pipelines and orchestration supports scalable and repeatable sensing experiments across multiple nodes and locations. 5TONIC also contributes to international standardization and open-source ecosystems. It actively supports European research and innovation through its involvement in SNS JU-funded and other Horizon Europe projects.

Collocated within 5TONIC is the SLICES-Madrid Research Infrastructure, offering several adaptable resources that enable ISAC. Relevant equipment includes: O-RAN compliant programmable B210/N310 Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP), a containerized 5G core running on powerful Commercial Off-The-Shelf (COTS) servers, UE emulation software that allows for the creation of many UEs, thereby enabling the stress testing of network capabilities under saturation conditions. We also can give access to a channel emulator to provide customized sensing environments that can replicate any real-life complex scenario. The infrastructure also supports the integration of commercial UEs, allowing for testing the real-world performance of active sensing solutions.

The 5TONIC and SLICES infrastructures are connected via microwave links to an indoor 5G experimental network at UC3M, as depicted in Figure 4. The latter enables research into passive-radio sensing relying on 5G broadcast channels including a gNB with wide coverage operating in the n78 band (3.5 GHz). The setup also includes four distributed remote radio heads (radio units) that provide MIMO diversity for improved spatial resolution. The radio units are connected to the baseband units via a 10GbE link. The latter supports GPS timing allowing for synchronized multi-sensor data fusion for enhanced ISAC solutions. The lab environment is replete with rich scatterers providing the ideal, realistic multipath sensing scenarios for testing ISAC systems developed in the context of the project.

Sensing Capabilities

This infrastructure allows to conduct passive sensing experiments by leveraging downlink radio signals such as Synchronization Signal Blocks (SSB) and Channel State Information Reference Signals (CSI-RS). In particular, it enables experiments on presence detection (gleaned from fluctuations in channel quality), human activity recognition, e.g. motion sensing and environmental mapping based on time-varying features of radio signals. Moreover, the setup allows for fusion of sensing data from Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN) APs and 5G gNBs as in Figure 5.

This setup offers a stable yet flexible testbed for developing and validating 5G-based passive sensing algorithms, with opportunities to explore spatial diversity, temporal coherence, and channel analytics in a controlled yet realistic environment.

Figure 4: SLICES-RI ISAC infrastructure at UC3M.

Figure 5: Multi-RAT passive sensing setup. A PSTA (red) collects signals from WLAN AP and 5G gNB (orange) to determine the position of a target (blue)

Sensing in Unlicensed bands

In order to enable research into sensing over unlicensed frequencies, the lab at UC3M employs 4 tri-band Ruckus R760 Access Points (APs) supporting 2.4, 5 and 6GHz operation modes. Additionally, the lab includes Turrus Omnia Wi-Fi 6E capable routers. These devices allow for multi-static passive sensing including:

- Operation in the 6 GHz band, providing high bandwidth and reduced interference compared to legacy Wi-Fi.
- Support for monitor mode and Channel State Information (CSI) extraction, enabling the capture of fine-grained signal variations without interfering with normal traffic.
- Deployment in a multi-static configuration, where multiple routers act as reference or listening points to observe the same signal from different spatial perspectives.
- Use of beacon frames and regular data traffic as opportunistic signals for sensing, enabling passive monitoring of environmental changes.

In addition to the sub-6 GHz 5G deployment, the indoor facilities at UC3M include MikroTik wAP 60G (see Figure 5) units operating in the 60 GHz band, installed to explore short-range, high-frequency radio links in realistic environments. These devices support wireless point-to-point (P2P) communication and are well-suited for passive sensing research that leverages CSI.

Key characteristics of the wAP 60G relevant to sensing include:

- Operation in the V-band (57–66 GHz), with wide channel bandwidth for high-resolution CSI, such as 2.16 GHz.

- Integrated beamforming antennas, enabling narrow-beam transmissions that are sensitive to changes in the surrounding environment.
- Ability to capture fine-grained CSI per frame, allowing signal variations to be studied under different movement and blockage conditions.
- Designed for short-range indoor coverage, which is ideal for localized sensing and experimental repeatability.

While these units do not provide phase-coherent data or Doppler estimation, they are effective for experiments involving:

- Presence detection and basic motion classification based on rapid CSI fluctuations.
- Multipath analysis in high-frequency environments, especially with reflective surfaces or human occlusion.
- Comparative studies between 60 GHz CSI and sub-6 GHz 5G signals in the same space, enabling multi-band fusion approaches.
- Fine Time Measurements (FTM)/ Angle of Arrival (AoA) estimations between different STAs and APs.

The UC3M passive sensing testbed, offers a complementary mmWave platform that broadens the spectrum of available signals for environmental perception research.

Overall, this configuration enables: (i) Simultaneous signal collection across multiple receivers to allow for spatial sensing diversity; (ii) multipoint human motion detection thereby facilitating robust presence detection and trajectory estimation; and (iii) enhanced scene analysis by fusing multiband signals (sub 6GHz and 60 GHz).

Figure 6: 60 GHz 802.11ad commercial devices tuned to perform sensing operations

4.1.2 IMDEA

Overview of Experimental Infrastructure

The IMDEA Networks Institute hosts a state-of-the-art experimental infrastructure tailored for end-to-end (E2E) wireless systems research, with a particular focus on emerging 6G paradigms such as ISAC. These facilities enable the full development cycle of MultiX signal processing enablers and PoCs, from real-time signal acquisition to data-driven algorithm validation.

IMDEA's platforms are designed with high flexibility and modularity, offering advanced capabilities in both sub-6 GHz and mmWave bands. The testbeds support monostatic, bistatic, and multi-static configurations and feature tight synchronization mechanisms, which are essential for sensing accuracy, distributed operation, and scalable data fusion. IMDEA's infrastructure also includes high-speed data links to host PCs and GPU-equipped servers for ML-based inference. The summary of the available technologies is provided in Table 3.

Table 3 Description of IMDEA Lab

Item	Description
ID	<i>IMDEA-01</i>
Name	<i>IMDEA Lab</i>
Description	<i>See testbed description</i>
Wireless technology	<i>3GPP (Sub-6 GHz, 24-28 GHz), non-3GPP (Sub-6 GHz, 60 GHz).</i>
MPS functionalities	<i>Multi-band (Sub-6 and 24-28 GHz or 60 GHz) monostatic, bistatic, multi-static</i>
Required software components	– <i>Matlab</i>
Output data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <i>IQ samples of received frames</i> – <i>Coherent channel estimation covering the different sub-bands</i> – <i>Channel estimation using different beam patterns (mmWave) which is enabler for passive / active localization.</i>
Layers covered	<i>Layer 1 PHY</i>

MultiX Innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Over-the-air synchronization techniques for bistatic setups.</i> – <i>Coherent / Non-coherent multi-band ISAC algorithms.</i>
Related Tests	– <i>Human localization and motion estimation based on multi-band and multi-static sensing.</i>
Current TRL	<i>TRL 3-4</i>
Targeted TRL	<i>TRL 4</i>

Multi-band and mmWave Platforms

IMDEA’s ISAC infrastructure primarily consists of two complementary platforms: mmFLEX and MIMORPH, both designed for advanced experimentation in high-frequency bands and for rapid adaptation to diverse sensing and communication use cases.

mmFLEX [1] is an Field-Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) based platform built around a high-end Vadatech chassis. It offers more than 2 GHz of instantaneous bandwidth and operates in the 58-70 GHz mmWave band. Main components are shown in Figure 7. The system integrates phased antenna arrays capable of analog beamforming, and it has been extended to function as a monostatic mmWave ISAC node. This platform has already enabled pioneering experiments in human activity recognition and classification, showcasing its utility in ISAC-oriented PoCs [2][3].

Figure 7: IMDEA's mmFLEX platform

MIMORPH [3], in contrast, is a highly versatile system built on Radio Frequency System-on-Chip (RFSoc) technology. It supports multiple operational modes, including:

- mmWave 4x4 MIMO with 2 GHz bandwidth per stream and analogue beamforming,
- Sub-6 GHz 8x8 MIMO,
- Multi-band configurations, simultaneously using both frequency regions.

This morphable functionality makes MIMORPH ideal for testing multi-technology setups, multi-band architectures, as shown in Figure 8, and the MultiX algorithms designed for joint processing across spatial and spectral domains. The platform is further enhanced by IMDEA's custom real-time PHY implementations targeting 5G-NR and beyond, enabling synchronized channel measurements across both FR1 and FR2.

Figure 8. IMDEA's Mimorph experimentation platform

Currently, IMDEA operates:

- 7 Xilinx RFSoc FPGA boards.
- 2 Vadatech FPGA platforms.
- 20 mmWave phased antenna arrays operating at 28 GHz and 60 GHz.
- Laboratory-grade RF instrumentation, including:
 - Signal generators.
 - High-bandwidth (8 GHz) oscilloscopes.
 - Real-time spectrum analysers.

Testbed Topologies and Deployment Modes

IMDEA's facilities are organized around modular reconfigurable testbeds capable of supporting a wide range of deployment scenarios: monostatic, bistatic and multi-static distributed sensing. These setups are used extensively to validate core signal processing modules in both lab-controlled and semi-realistic environments, offering indoor and outdoor deployment options.

Indoor Lab Setup with Modular components allow indoor experiments in a dedicated laboratory space equipped with:

- RF absorbing panels that help control reflections and suppress multipath, enabling reproducible measurements for communication and sensing.
- Pan-tilt positioning systems for automated beam scanning, angular resolution experiments, and calibration routines.
- Extended low-loss RF cabling, which allows flexible arrangement of antennas and front-ends across a wide area.
- A centralized control server running a custom MATLAB-based orchestration suite, which manages signal generation, beam configurations, data acquisition, and FPGA communication in real time.

Figure 9 Indoor experimentation

Outdoor deployments for realistic scenarios: for field experiments, based on IMDEA's platforms are designed to be deployed outdoors, where the same core architecture is extended to support:

- Battery-powered operation of RFSoc nodes for autonomous sensing and transmission.
- Extended SubMiniature version A (SMA) and control cables to position antennas or sub-arrays away from the processing units, e.g., on tripods or building facades.
- Continued centralized management from the same MATLAB server, either locally or remotely via Ethernet/Wi-Fi links, enabling seamless reuse of experimental code and configuration profiles from indoor campaigns.

Figure 10: Example outdoor deployment

Multi-Band, Multi-Antenna, and Multi-Node Capabilities

The IMDEA infrastructure is inherently designed to support MultiX experimentation. Specifically, it enables combined operation across multiple frequency bands, antenna arrays, and distributed node configurations. IMDEA's platforms span a wide frequency range (sub-6 GHz, 24-28 GHz and 57-70 GHz mmWave), enabling seamless transition and co-existence between communication and sensing signals. The MIMORPH testbed allows for simultaneous multi-band experimentation, where mmWave and sub-6 GHz RF chains are active in parallel, enabling heterogeneous signal processing and data fusion across channels with different propagation properties. This allows to explore ISAC trade-offs between resolution (mmWave) and robustness (sub-6 GHz), a key requirement in MultiX.

IMDEA's platforms support a wide variety of MIMO configurations:

- 8×8 MIMO system at sub-6 GHz, or as a 4×4 mmWave MIMO system with 2 GHz per spatial stream.
- Flexible subarray layouts (especially at the receiver), enabling near-field experiments, aperture synthesis, and virtual array construction.

IMDEA's testbeds support deployment in multi-node configurations, enabling distributed ISAC experimentation with tightly coordinated timing. To achieve synchronization across physically separated nodes, the platforms employ several complementary techniques:

- Over-the-air synchronization is used in scenarios where RF cabling is impractical. This method relies on the presence of known static reflectors in the environment, allowing multiple nodes to align their timing references by detecting predictable echoes or reference signals, even without a wired trigger.

- In wired setups, synchronization is maintained using long low-loss cables between spatially separated nodes. This allows reference clocks or triggers to be physically distributed while keeping the signal integrity and timing accuracy intact. These setups enable the construction of flexible geometries such as bistatic, linear, or distributed MIMO arrays with shared time and frequency references.
- In multi-band experiments, where both sub-6 GHz and mmWave channels are active, synchronization is achieved at the clock level by assigning both transmitter and receiver functionalities to the same RFSoc device. This ensures tight alignment between the two frequency domains without requiring additional hardware synchronization layers.

Combined with the centralized MATLAB-based orchestration system, these synchronization strategies enable precise control of timing and coordination across heterogeneous nodes, making it possible to test advanced ISAC scenarios such as multi-view sensing and cross-band fusion, all of which are integral to the MultiX vision.

Figure 11: Example of synchronization on a multi-static ISAC deployment

Key Sensing Metrics

The hardware design of the system and software pipeline enable precise measurement of several performance indicators critical to ISAC, as indicated in Table 4:

Table 4 Supported sensing metrics and capabilities

Metric	Capability
Range resolution	< 10 cm at 60 GHz with 2 GHz bandwidth

Doppler resolution	< 0.1 m/s with 50 ms integration time
Angular resolution	< 1 degree with mmWave analog beam steering
Sensing refresh rate	Up-to 2 KHz depending on frame configuration
SNR and sensitivity	Configurable depending on waveform power and front-end gain

Real-Time Processing and Data Access

All sensing modes are tightly coupled with the MATLAB orchestration layer, which provides:

- Streaming and storage of raw In-Phase (I) and Quadrature (Q) (IQ) samples for offline processing.
- On-device pre-processing for basic packet detection and filtering.

Perception Algorithms and Multi-Sensor Fusion

IMDEA's infrastructure is designed to support the end-to-end development of sensing and perception algorithms, with a strong emphasis on offline processing of raw IQ data. Rather than focusing on real-time applications, the platforms enable large-scale data collection and post-processing, which is essential for building, testing, and refining advanced ISAC algorithms in the MultiX project.

Post-Processing Pipeline and Algorithmic Tools

All sensing experiments are configured to store unprocessed IQ samples at high speed. These datasets are then analysed offline using MATLAB, Python, and other custom tools. This approach enables:

- High-resolution range-Doppler-angle mapping, using FFT-based and subspace-based techniques, such as MULTiple Signal Classification (MUSIC) or Estimation of Signal Parameters via Rotational Invariance Technique (ESPRIT).
- Motion profiling and micro-Doppler analysis, enabling the characterization of fine-grained target movements (e.g., gait cycles).
- Target detection and tracking, using traditional detection algorithms (CFAR, energy thresholding) or learning-based pipelines.

IMDEA's platforms also support advanced data fusion across sensors and frequency bands, enabled by synchronized measurements and structured data capture:

- Subarrays and spatially distributed receivers collect multi-perspective views of the scene, enabling offline fusion for angle estimation, diversity gains, or redundancy analysis.
- Multi-band fusion (e.g., combining mmWave and sub-6 GHz observations) is achieved by leveraging synchronized acquisition across the RF chains.
- Custom fusion pipelines can be built in MATLAB or Python, applying late fusion, weighted averaging, or feature-level merging based on the nature of the sensing task.

4.2 UC/IHP Open Lab – ISAC research laboratory

The UC/IHP Open Lab is a research and development infrastructure that is deployed both at UC facilities and at IHP. The former part of the lab is a B5G playground where novel technologies that are tested at IHP can be integrated and evaluated as part of an O-RAN 3GPP testbed. The latter part of the lab is dedicated to build up technologies for ISAC, currently targeting OFDM-based solutions at Sub-6 and mmWave (60 GHz) and OTFS-based solutions (Sub-6).

The central part of the testbed resides at UC and it is based on a BubbleRAN (BR) platform, which is an advanced Multi-x¹ (MX)2 5G network infrastructure. This platform is based on a multi-x platform development kit (MX-PDK), and presents a diverse range of both open-source and commercial network components. The 5G RAN and CN-supported SW stacks include OAI and Lite-On commercial solutions.

Figure 12 shows a sketch of the available testbeds at the UC that are described in the following subsections. ① refers to the non-3GPP ISAC technologies that have been developed at IHP and deployed at UC, while ② depicts the BR platform to which 3GPP-based O-RUs can be attached. The sensing and MultiX extensions of the facility are described in Table 5.

¹ Multi-x may refer to multi-vendor and multi-version, and may also refer to may also refer to multi-node, multi-distribution, multi-runtime, multi-cloud, and multi-instance

[D4.1] - Open Labs design and integration and validation methodology

Figure 12 UC/IHP ISAC testbed, ① Sub-6 ISAC and mmWave testbeds, ② BR platform, ③ Planned integration of an SDR-based O-RU from Massive Beams

Table 5 Description of IHP Open Lab

Item	Description
ID	IHPUC-01
Name	IHP/UC Open Lab
Description	See testbed description
Wireless technology	3GPP (Sub-6 GHz), non-3GPP (Sub-6 GHz), non-3GPP (Sub-6 GHz, OTFS-based), variant of 802.11ad (60GHz)
MPS functionalities	Multi-band (Sub-6 and 60 GHz) monostatic

DASH Services	<i>Sensing data {fusion, transformation, processing} and sensing results exposure (Under discussion)</i>
Required software components	– <i>GnuRADIO</i>
Output data	– <i>Presence detection notification a human being inside a room using the monostatic radar capabilities</i> – <i>Extension to sensing using SRS signals</i>
Layers covered	<i>Layer 1 PHY - Layer 7 (application)</i>
MultiX Innovations	– <i>Joint optimization of connectivity and dynamic processing for multi-sensor data fusion</i> – <i>Orthogonal Time Frequency Space (OTFS) localization and sensing for high-mobility scenarios</i> – <i>Inter-band multiband ISAC algorithms</i>
Related Tests	– <i>Presence detection</i>
Current TRL	<i>TRL 3-4</i>
Targeted TRL	<i>TRL 4</i>

4.2.1 Sub-6 GHz ISAC testbed

A Sub-6 GHz sensing system, developed in the context of the BeGREEN project [12], is extended in the context of MultiX to benefit from multi-node cooperative perception and sensing data sharing from multiple sensing nodes. The sensing system implementation has been performed using a USRP N321 Software Defined Radios (SDRs). The developed system is shown in Figure 13. Four SDRs are used to obtain a total of 8 receive channels, given that each radio has only two receiver channels.

All the SDRs share the same Local Oscillator (LO). This is achieved by generating the LO at one of the SDRs and using cables to distribute it to the other SDRs. It is necessary to calibrate the phases between the different SDRs, since they will have random phases due to tolerances of the electronic components built in them. This calibration will allow fully coherent operation of the SDRs, needed to perform beamforming.

The timing synchronization between the SDRs is achieved using the White Rabbit (WR) protocol, i.e. using a WR Ethernet switch model WRS-3/18². With this approach, the SDRs time can be synchronized with precision of ± 100 ps, which is sufficient for the current application.

Figure 13 ISAC Sub-6 system

The carrier frequency is in the 5 GHz Industrial, Scientific and Medical (ISM) radio band, since no explicit licence is needed for transmitting in this band. The lower 5 GHz ISM band is preferred, as it allows increasing the output power compared to the high 5 GHz band, resulting in an output power of not more than 10 dBm.

The ranging precision of the sensing system is proportional to the available bandwidth. In the 5 GHz ISM band, channel bandwidths of up to 160 MHz are available and bandwidths of 320 MHz are envisioned. These N321 SDRs are supporting bandwidths of up to 200 MHz and this value is used in the experiments. For sensing, different waveforms can be used. In this case a maximum length sequence, with length of 16383 bits, i.e. one symbol, was transmitted. This sequence is modulated using Binary Phase-Shift Keying (BPSK) modulation. A Uniform Linear Array (ULA) consisting of 8 patch antennas was designed and manufactured, being the distance between the antennas of $\lambda/2$.

4.2.2 mmWave ISAC testbed

This section presents a mmWave ISAC testbed that is based on the mmWave SDR platform from [13], built using RFSoc Ultrascale+ FPGA ZCU111 (Gen1) from Xilinx and a dual-module analog antenna frontend equipped with two Sivers BFM06005 60 GHz phased array beam-steering modules [14] (see Figure 14). It features all Digital Signal Processing (DSP) in a single System-on-Chip (SoC), thus minimizing the form factor. It is based on a COTS evaluation board (FPGA-based) and front-end modules. The developed mmWave ISAC system is depicted in Figure 14. The extensions to support ISAC in the testbed were implemented in the context of the German-funded project Open6GHub [14]. The platform supports both SDR and real-time

² <https://safran-navigation-timing.com/product/white-rabbit-switch-low-jitter/>

(RT) operation modes]. The HW-based processing is capable of reaching multi-Gbps data throughput and a short sensing time of below 0.5 ms when sweeping the 63 beams.

Figure 14 a) Xilinx RFSoc ZCU 111 board with SDR functionality and HW implemented real-time OFDM baseband processor, b) 60 GHz dual-module full-duplex RF frontend

4.2.3 OTFS ISAC testbed

An OTFS-based ISAC is available at IHP Open Lab, where the OTFS waveform on USRP X310 SDR [16] are implemented. The system targets a realistic monostatic scenario at a base station with separate Tx and Rx antennas (for communication and RADAR) at 5 GHz carrier frequency. It allows performing single and multi-target sensing. A single USRP device (Ettus x310) is used to implement the OTFS-based sensing system. A script allows to utilize USRP Hardware Driver (UHD) drivers for synchronization, and the received sensing samples from the device can be imported into MATLAB for OTFS processing. A UBX-160 daughterboard is utilized with a USRP X310, which provides a maximum bandwidth of 160 MHz and covers carrier frequencies of up to 6 GHz. The maximum supportable sampling rate is of 200 MSps, with an occupied bandwidth of 150 MHz.

Figure 15 shows a setup of the OTFS ISAC testbed in an indoor office scenario. In such scenario, there may exist multiple reflectors present in the environment, e.g., walls, floors, tables, doors, etc. These unwanted reflections can degrade the results, viz. accuracy of results. This experimental setup of OTFS for ISAC considers the sensing at the base station so it can identify multiple users, reflectors, and moving objects in the environment.

Figure 15 OTFS SDR System in indoor Office Environment, a) Experimental setup for OTFS ISAC, b) Tx and Rx antennas, c) Receiver with reflector

4.2.4 5G NR ISAC testbed

Regarding the activities that are being carried out in the context of the project, we can distinguish between the work in two different 5G NR ISAC testbeds, described in the following two sections.

4.2.4.1 OAI-based 5G NR

One of the testbeds is based on a standard 5G SA implementation of OAI using Ettus N321 devices, where a gNB is able to communicate with a UE and, simultaneously, is able to receive the reflected signals to perform sensing (monostatic). A sketch of the implementation is shown in Figure 16 and it is ongoing work carried out in the 6G-SENSES³ project.

³ <https://6g-senses.eu/>

Figure 16 OAI-based 5G NR with sensing capabilities

4.2.5 OAI-based O-RAN

The OAI-based O-RAN ISAC testbed residing at the UC comprises the BR components MX-RAN, MX-CN, MX-Operator, and MX-RIC. These components will be leveraged and their implementation will be tailored to integrate an ISAC service model implementation sensing Apps, implemented as xApps.

The UC/IHP testbed is able to accommodate different RUs:

1. the N321 RUs that will act as radar-based sensing nodes. It includes the Sub-6 GHz (non-3GPP) sensing system (based on that described in section 4.2.1) and the mmWave node described in section 4.2.2.
2. commercial O-RUs (LITEON) interoperable with BR ecosystem to gather sensing information.
3. an O-RAN O-RU SDR White Box System from Massive Beams⁴. This platform will allow, with the scope of providing an increased openness and flexibility of an O-RAN-based RU, to perform additional tasks at RU level such as modifiable signal processing blocks for 5G-NR low-PHY baseband signal processing and can incorporate sensing functions at PHY layer. The integration of this system is planned for 2026.

4.3 Networked Systems Open Lab

4.3.1 Distributed Massive MIMO

The Networked System Open Lab at KU Leuven has a Distributed Massive MIMO testbed (depicted in Figure 17). While the initial testbed was a fully centralized Massive MIMO deployment, several upgrades over the last years have enabled:

⁴ [White box system](#)

- the distribution of antenna systems for many types of topologies including Uniform Linear Array (ULA), Uniform Planar Array (UPA), Cell-free, etc.
- the extension of data logging capabilities so that longer measurements are possible (needed for sensing and Doppler processing).
- the addition of a positioning system to allow for precise location labelling of targets or transmitters.
- the creation of an over-the-air sync method to enable Massive MIMO measurements with a drone-mounted UE.

The work presented in [28] **iError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** gives an overview of the capabilities and dataset of this Distributed Massive MIMO testbed. The code used for this magazine is also available from IEEE Code Ocean [6]. The code offers functionality for different user scheduling methods, and also different MIMO precoders. It is a very good starting point to start developing other precoders or beamformers.

Figure 17: Massive MIMO testbed

4.3.2 mmWave testbed

The mmWave testbed, depicted in Figure 18, comprises of two main components: Baseband and RF front-end modules. The baseband module is built on the Zynq UltraScale+ RFSoc ZCU111, integrating multiple Analog-to-Digital and Digital-to-Analog (AD/DA) converters capable of giga sample rates, meeting high throughput requirements in mmWave communication. This enables:

- 2T2R MIMO.
- Analog beamforming and beam sweeping.

- Monostatic/bistatic sensing.
- MATLAB implemented 11ad baseband.

Figure 18: KUL mmWave testbed

4.3.3 6G Real-time Flexible Radio Access Network REF-RAN

The 6G Real-time Flexible Radio Access Network (6G-REFRAN) testbed, depicted in Figure 19, offers a new facility for Real-time Flexible Radio Access Network research. It is aiming towards:

- Large data logging capability for being able to sense a lot of data for long periods of time.
- Scalability measured in terms of the level of distribution of the Radio Unit (RU), with and without sync.
- Remote access of the data server for training AI models.
- Remote access of the radios for remote experiments.

Figure 19: 6G REF-RAN testbed architecture

The X410s provide high bandwidth (400 MHz) and local compute power. A central server offers central compute power for AI as a service, learning on datasets that are made public.

The infrastructure of our testbed, depicted in Figure 19, consists of a main computer, to perform computation and control, and a set of USRPs, which can operate as RUs. This main computer is an HP Enterprise Edge server configuration featuring a dual Xeon Gold 6430 processors boasting 32 cores and 64 threads in total. The machine has 1TB of DDR5 PC5-4800-2R memory and 960GB SATA SSD storage. The connectivity between the controller and the RUs is provided by a dedicated high-speed 100GbE fibre link. Furthermore, a 1Gb Ethernet interface is designated for control purposes.

The main computer not only provides the core operational aspects of the testbed but also the software and hardware for ML, and data processing. Users are able can perform number crunching and AI training using an NVIDIA A100 accelerator card, in conjunction with Tensor Flow or PyTorch. Data sets are stored locally and are accessible to the public, ensuring transparency and availability.

To ensure precision in timing and synchronization, a Rubidium clock governs the entire testbed. However, remote synchronization over the air is an active area of research.

Accessibility to the testbed is offered remotely via SSH, contingent upon the creation of an account with the IT services. Account requests can be directed to the KU Leuven team for provisioning. Moreover, in collaboration with Intracom, the testbed will be accessible via the p-Edge infrastructure for remote control and experimentation.

The radio units are USRP X410 by National Instruments. They are capable of operating either in a stand-alone (embedded) mode or as host-based systems with network streaming capabilities. These units cover a frequency range from 1 MHz to 7.2 GHz, with tunability extending up to 8 GHz. The RUs have an instantaneous bandwidth capacity of up to 400 MHz.

The testbed can run any software designed for USRP X410 radios. The software we get from NI is:

- USRP drivers.
- Data collection API (to record samples directly from USRP): <https://github.com/genesys-neu/ni-rf-data-recording-api>
- RFmx Waveform Creator⁵ to generate the correct waveforms.

4.3.4 Sensing ground truth facility

To facilitate data logging, both 5G and 6G testbeds are linked with localization and motion capture systems, shown in Figure 20. Both a localization system and motion capture systems

⁵ <https://www.ni.com/en/support/downloads/software-products/download.rfmx-waveform-creator.html#494513>

are available. Testing of the synchronization of the motion capture system with any of the testbeds is still ongoing.

Various experiments have been conducted with the 5G and localization system. Below, details of the systems are given.

Figure 20: Accurate positioning infrastructure for Joint Communication and Sensing Research

Figure 21: The CNC positioner and MoCAP systems

XY-Table

The localisation system selected is a Computer Numerical Controlled (CNC) positioner, depicted in Figure 21. The user antenna moves with high positioning accuracy and reliability on the 2D plane where the positioner is deployed. The main downside of this system is that it limits the locations of the user to the area of the CNC-positioner. However, CNC-positioner is relatively inexpensive and can thus be used in larger numbers to effectively increase the measurement area. We deployed four CNC positioners simultaneously in a grid-like configuration.

The selected CNC positioner is the Open-Builds ACRO 1515. Each positioner reliably covers a 1250 x 1250 mm area, covering a total of 2.5 by 2.5 m only (very dense). Furthermore, the reported error of the positioner is less than 0.1 mm. Custom brackets hold the legs of multiple positioners in place so that their relative position is known.

The positioner and the 5G testbed have been fully integrated, so that logging of the channel data from the testbed is synchronised with the positioning system. A holder is also available to rotate the positioners in the vertical direction, so that experiments emulating reflective intelligent surfaces type of reflectors can be set up.

MOCAP system

Accurate positioning of the user is also ensured by using a motion capture system (Qualisys Miquis M3 with 4 cameras), for sub mm position. Cameras are arranged all around the room but can be moved around to capture different scenarios, shown in Figure 19. The cameras have 2 Mpixel (1824 x 1088 resolution) and capture Infrared (IR) video at 340 fps. They can correctly resolve positions with 0.11 mm precision in 3D. The maximum range is 15 m.

The MoCAP system consists of four Miquis cameras⁶ and massive sensors, where all cameras are perfectly synchronized and the sensors can be deployed on the human body. In general, the system enables 6-DoF tracking (3D position and 3D orientation) using 3 or more lightweight retro-reflective infrared markers, and the accuracy is below 0.5 mm. Moreover, its field-of-view with standard lens 64x41°, with the maximum detection distance of 15 m. Therefore, the MoCAP system not only provides visual data for multisensory fusion but also provide the ground truth for the proof of concept of eHealth or Smart homes applications.

The system comes with a dedicated software to capture data and it is compatible with MATLAB and Python. Data capture can be synchronised to the same time reference used by the testbed. It is compatible with other radio systems via the Ethernet interface.

⁶ <https://www.qualisys.com/cameras/miquis/#tech-specs>

4.4 Other testing facilities

4.4.1 STC Technikum

The Technikum is a state-of-the-art testing and demonstration facility located within the Siemens Technology Center (STC) in Garching. Designed as a shared innovation space, it serves multiple research departments, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and rapid prototyping.

This versatile lab environment is equipped with advanced technologies including:

- An indoor 5G campus network for high-speed, low-latency connectivity.
- Edge cloud compute resources enabling real-time data processing and AI applications.
- A robot arm for automation and robotics research.
- Multiple Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) for logistics and mobility experiments.

The Technikum supports both experimental research and live demonstrations, making it a dynamic hub for showcasing cutting-edge industrial solutions. Its infrastructure is tailored to support scalable, future-oriented developments in areas such as digitalization, automation, and connectivity.

In MultiX, the demo space in the Technikum is undergoing a significant technological upgrade to become a leading-edge platform for ISAC. The primary 5G system is provided by BR, featuring a flexible gNB architecture with built-in radio sensing capabilities for object detection and localization. This system includes a RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) implementation, enabling dynamic network optimization through modular xApps and rApps. Complementing this, UC3M will integrate a Wi-Fi-based sensing system operating in the mmWave frequency range, that utilizes CSI for motion detection and environmental monitoring.

Additionally, NEC will provide a Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS), that will be integrated into the network control loop, allowing real-time adaptation to environmental, radio propagation and user context. Together, these enhancements position the Technikum as a well-suited experimentation environment enabling joint communication and sensing, AI-driven network control, and reconfigurable radio environments, for deploying and showcasing the PoC1, a Multi-Layer Digital Twin (ML-DT) for industrial manufacturing.

4.4.2 i2CAT facilities

i2CAT in Barcelona comprises within its premises several laboratories able to test and demonstrate RAN and Autonomous Guided Vehicle (AGV) related technologies. Related research areas using these facilities include Smart Networks and Services, Distributed AI and AI-Driven Systems, Cybersecurity and Space Communications.

For the experiments planned in these facilities the main hardware includes quadruped and wheeled robots to serve as mobile sensor and radio equipment platforms, stationary software-defined radio equipment to create the mock-up networks, and commercial e-health sensors to track the vital signs of the monitored individuals.

Within MultiX, this space is being configured as an ISAC platform, exposing gNB functions to deploy object detection and localization and data transmission to assess the viability of the architecture designs.

4.4.3 InterDigital Lab

The ISAC testbed, depicted in Figure 22, is designed as a demonstration platform to showcase advanced 6G use cases that merge communication and sensing capabilities. It emphasizes 3GPP-Wi-Fi convergence, enabling seamless sensing continuity across indoor and outdoor environments. The testbed serves both as a research vehicle and as an MWC'26 showcase, highlighting InterDigital's leadership in ISAC and its value in licensing-driven business domains such as smartphones, consumer electronics, IoT/automotive, and cloud services. The core objectives of this testbed facility are to:

- **Showcase 3GPP-Wi-Fi Complementarity:** Demonstrating how 3GPP (cellular) and Wi-Fi sensing can interwork to provide continuous and reliable sensing services across environments.
- **Validate ISAC Use Cases:** Experiment with scenarios relevant to telecom operators, industrial robotics, and retail analytics.
- **Highlight Business Opportunities:** Expose how ISAC enables new services for MNOs, service providers, and verticals like retail and manufacturing.
- **Link to Standards and Ecosystem:** Align with ETSI ISAC ISG, 3GPP SA1, and IEEE 802.11bf specifications while building on partnerships with European operators.

Figure 22: Testbed scenario at InterDigital Lab

Figure 23: ISAC Testbed Workflow at InterDigital Lab

In Table 5 we summarize the sensing capabilities and setup of the lab.

Table 5 InterDigital Lab Description

Item	Description
ID	<i>IDE-01</i>
Name	<i>InterDigital Lab</i>
Description	<i>See testbed description</i>
Wireless technology	<i>3GPP (sub 6GHz), Wi-Fi (60GHz), distance sensor (laser-based proximity sensor)</i>
MPS functionalities	<i>Multi-band (3GPP and Wi-Fi), bi-static (3GPP), multi-static (Wi-Fi)</i>
DASH Services	<i>Sensing data {fusion, transformation, processing} and sensing results exposure</i>
Required software components	<i>GnuRADIO</i>
Output data	<i>- Presence detection notification a human being inside a room including their relative position to the sensing receiver</i>
Layers covered	<i>Layer 1 PHY – Layer 7 (application)</i>
Related Tests	<i>- Human presence detection and localisation determination</i>
Current TRL	<i>TRL 3</i>
Targeted TRL	<i>TRL 4</i>

5 PoC 1 Multi-layer Network Digital Twin for Industrial Manufacturing

This PoC aims to showcase the application of some of the techniques developed in the project to drive efficiency, sustainability, and growth within industrial manufacturing settings. The experiments cover the design of a Digital Twin (DT) platform as a virtual representation of selected aspects of the real world and the use of multi-sensor systems for industrial applications of mobile robots. Its purpose is the provisioning of side-information, or context, which is pertinent to a given (industrial) application or (communication) service. This in turn enables proactive identification and resolution of potential issues, allows for improved decision-making, and enables configuration based on specific circumstances and predicted events, leading to enhanced efficiency and productivity.

A DT of the wireless network can enable fast and proactive adjustment of communication services to a dynamic and challenging industrial (radio) environment, paving the way towards a deterministic behaviour of wireless networks and highly reliable applications with guaranteed performance running with their help.

The DT is designed as a multi-layered and potentially distributed platform (see Figure 24). It is linked to the DASH, which hosts contextual information from the network, the application, and the environment. Such context information is gained from the MPS, which aggregates and fuses sensor data from various sources, including ISAC and other discrete sensors. The output of the DT are digital artifacts that can be consumed either by an app or a service which creates value for the user by inducing changes in the real world through one or more devices.

Figure 24: Multi-Layer Digital Twin framework and its interaction with the real world.

In this PoC, we implement a Multi-layer Digital Twin (ML-DT) for Industrial Manufacturing scenario (see Figure 25), where machines are jointly performing an industrial task, e.g., autonomous material delivery, within a changing environment. Each robot individually lacks the capabilities to perform the task, e.g., robot A is stationary and robot B may have limited sensing capabilities. In this scenario, wireless communication is employed to exchange messages between robot A, robot B and the ML-DT with the DASH.

Figure 25: Reference scenario for PoC 1.

To put this into practice, robot B has the task to deliver a workpiece to Robot A. The challenge here is that the environment is changing (see movable obstacle) and the task execution needs to be adapted to that change. Due to its limited on-board sensing capabilities, Robot B relies on external support by the MPS, which is fed by ISAC and other external sensor data, to detect the changing environment and to complete its task under the new conditions.

To enable seamless collaboration, the robots communicate and coordinate their actions through the ML-DT. In this PoC, we focus on three DT layers or slices: The environment DT gets information including changes about the real environment via the MPS. This information is

provided to the network DT as well as the (industrial) application DT, to adapt the network according to the changes in the radio environment, and to adapt the task execution according to the new environmental conditions, respectively.

The final PoC will be showcased at the STC in Garching (Munich), highlighting how intelligent infrastructure and inter-robot collaboration can overcome individual limitations and enhance operational efficiency in automated environments.

5.1 Targeted demos

This section describes the demos showcasing the value of using a ML-DT in industrial manufacturing. The demos are organized in one or more experiments, which prove the functionality of the key functions. The related experiments are described in the next section.

The PoC 1 consists of two demonstrations:

5.1.1 Demo 1: ML-DT for Operation of Wireless Networks

This demo showcases how a ML-DT platform can proactively optimize wireless network operations in a dynamic industrial environment. The DT aggregates contextual information from the application layer, communication systems, and environmental sensors to build a real-time representation of the network and its surroundings. Using this representation, the system aims to predict radio propagation, identify obstacles, and adjust network parameters such as RAT switching, RIS adjustment, and MAC-level resource management. The goal is to achieve deterministic wireless behaviour, improve QoS, and support mission-critical industrial applications with high reliability and low latency.

This demo is organized in experiments 1, 2, and 4, as described in sections 5.2.1, 5.2.2, and 5.2.4, respectively.

5.1.2 Demo 2: ML-DT for Collaborating Robots in Flexible Manufacturing

This demo illustrates how autonomous robots can collaborate using the DT to perform joint industrial tasks – such as material delivery – despite having limited individual sensing capabilities. Robot B, for example, relies on ISAC data and external sensors from Robot A, with coordination facilitated by the DT. The sensor data are coming from multiple sources (e.g. camera, lidar, ISAC) and are processed/fused by the MPS. The DT can request such MPS data from the DASH via service requests. By using such MPS data, the DT enables joint decision-making and guiding the robots through complex environments. This demonstration highlights the potential of perception-driven communication and sensing to support flexible manufacturing and autonomous systems.

This demo is going to be executed through experiments 1, 3, and 4, described in sections 5.2.1, 5.2.3, and 5.2.4, respectively.

5.2 Targeted experiments

The following experiments implement the main features for the PoC 1 reference scenario, shown in Figure 25.

5.2.1 Experiment 1: Environmental and radio awareness

In the context of advanced industrial communication and localization systems, the integration of multi-modal sensing technologies plays a pivotal role in enabling precise environmental awareness and adaptive network behaviour. Thus, Experiment 1 establishes the foundational mechanisms upon which the subsequent experiments are built. This phase focuses on aggregating, processing, and utilizing sensing data from various sources to generate accurate location information for both, active objects like the robots as well as passive obstacles like the moving wall, within a defined environment.

The data acquisition process involves the deployment of diverse sensing modalities, including lidar, camera systems, and ISAC technologies. These sources collectively contribute to a rich dataset that captures spatial and contextual information from the environment. The raw sensing data are transmitted to the MPS, which serves as the central unit for sensor fusion and interpretation. Through sophisticated algorithms, the MPS processes and integrates the heterogeneous data streams to derive up-to-date location information for the robots (esp. the AGV) and passive obstacles (esp. the moving wall).

Once the location data are synthesized, they are made accessible via the DASH service interface. The DASH responds to service requests by providing real-time location information of identified objects. This capability ensures that various system components (e.g. the ML-DT) can retrieve spatial data on demand, facilitating coordinated operations and situational awareness.

The ML-DT component leverages the location information provided by DASH to maintain an up-to-date representation of the physical environment. Specifically, it retrieves the position data of the robots and the moving obstacle, which is used to continuously refine the environmental map. This dynamic updating process allows the ML-DT to reflect real-world changes with high fidelity, thereby supporting accurate modelling and simulation tasks.

A key function of the ML-DT is its ability to adapt the radio propagation behaviour based on the updated environment map. By incorporating the latest environmental updates, the ML-DT recalculates the radio map, which includes metrics like the location-based distribution of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR). This up-to-date radio map is essential for optimizing communication performance, particularly in dynamic industrial settings where signal conditions can vary significantly due to physical obstructions and mobility patterns.

The fundamental validation methodology is outlined in Section 3.1. This experiment primarily concentrates on two areas: the system's environmental awareness and its radio awareness capability. For environmental awareness, the aim is to evaluate the accuracy of location information provided by the MPS and to examine the latency between an environmental

change (such as repositioning a wall) and the availability of updated location information via the DASH interface. To assess the radio awareness capability, we intend to measure the delay of the prediction process on the radio conditions. Additionally, we compare these predictions with actual measured radio conditions to determine the reliability and accuracy of the system’s radio environment modelling.

Experiment 1 thus serves as the basis for the entire PoC-1, thus, it contributes to both, Demo 1 and Demo 2 (cf. Section 5.1). Its outputs – namely, the location information generated by the MPS and disseminated via DASH, as well as the radio map generated by the ML-DT – are the main ingredients for the execution of the subsequent experiments.

A summary of Experiment 1 is highlighted in Table 6:

Table 6 Environmental and radio awareness experiment summary

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC1-EXP1</i>
Name	<i>Environmental and radio awareness</i>
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collection of sensing data from various sources: lidar, camera, Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), 3GPP network signals, ISAC. • Sensing data are processed and fused. This can be done for example on-device or externally, by MPS to obtain location information of moving robots or passive objects and obstacles. • Measure coverage in different scenarios related to industrial environments, for GNSS and 3GPP networks using hardware loaded on the test robot. • Evaluate the energy efficiency gain when applying sensor-selection strategies. • The DASH offers location information of objects via service requests. • The ML-DT retrieves location information of robots and passive moving obstacle to update the environment map. • The ML-DT uses the updated environment map to update the radio propagation behaviour, i.e. to get an updated radio map (e.g. based on SNR distribution). • Experiment 1 is the basis for the remaining experiments, which rely on the location information provided by the MPS.

DASH Services (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Request location information of robots and (passive) moving obstacle
MPS Technologies (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Multi-static, multi-band, multi-technology sensing Sensor fusion of raw data to obtain position information of AGV and moving obstacle.
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Location information of passive obstacle (moving wall) Location information of robots
Targeted KPIs/KVIs (WP1)	<p>KPI: Accuracy of positioning estimates by sensing: 0.1 m</p> <p>KPI: Sensing service latency: ≤ 100 ms</p> <p>KVI: Enhanced sensing capability of robots via ML-DT</p>
Related Testbeds	5TONIC, STC Technikum, i2CAT own infrastructure, InterDigital Lab
Targeted TRL	TRL 3-4

5.2.2 Experiment 2: Utilization of Multi-layer DT in Communications

Experiment 1 detects changes in the radio environment. This is the basis for experiment 2, where the ML-DT utilizes the radio awareness capability to explore different network parameter adaptations to optimize the current industrial setting in terms of communication behaviour.

A change in the physical environment is introduced with the deliberate movement or placement of a mobile wall. The primary objective is to simulate how evolving conditions in a factory or industrial plant may impact network performance and reliability. In response, the ML-DT acts as a central intelligence, orchestrating updates to its virtual representation of the environment. This begins with a service request to the DASH system, which provides up-to-date location information of any obstacles present (see experiment 1). By maintaining an accurate, real-time digital map of the environment, the ML-DT ensures that all subsequent adaptations are based on the latest situational data.

Once the updated environmental map is established, the ML-DT proceeds to update the radio map accordingly. This radio map serves as a foundational resource, reflecting the current state of wireless signal propagation across the industrial space. It considers changes of the signal attenuation, reflection, refraction, and shadowing introduced by the newly positioned obstacle (wall). By leveraging this layer of digital abstraction, the system can detect and anticipate wireless coverage gaps or signal degradation that would otherwise compromise network performance.

To counteract the negative impact of environmental changes, the ML-DT initiates a series of adaptive measures to provide the targeted network performance. We plan to evaluate the following network adaptation measures: The first one involves switching to an alternative RAT. In case the newly introduced wall is blocking the 5G signal, a transition to Wi-Fi could be enacted, ensuring continuity of service without manual intervention. For the second measure, the ML-DT can adjust a RIS, which further enhances wireless signal propagation by dynamically manipulating radio waves to circumvent the newly introduced obstacle and optimize coverage. Finally, the ML-DT is enhanced by the capability to impact resource allocation mechanisms. This is going to be achieved by making use of the O-RAN RIC architecture. Therefore, an xApp tries to recalibrate the resource allocation such that the QoS profile is optimized to reliably support the industrial application.

Before these adaptations are implemented in the physical network, the ML-DT first tests and refines them in the digital environment by updating and reassessing the radio map. This cycle of simulation and adjustment helps ensure that the intended network changes will achieve the desired improvements before being applied in reality.

There are two stages of using the ML-DT in communications: The first one is reactive, i.e., the application is already blocked due to a degraded communication performance. The ML-DT detects that situation and gets the application out of that blocking situation by reactively adapting the network to recover the communication performance such that the application can successfully finish the task. The second one is proactive, i.e., the ML-DT tries to avoid such blocking situations proactively, by predicting the communication performance and adapting the network in advance (if necessary), to maintain the communication performance throughout the entire task execution.

To validate this experiment, our objective is to evaluate the improvement of the network performance (e.g. SNR, measured delay and/or delay violation probability or packet error rate) for specific areas, before and after the network adaptation measures have been applied. Additionally, we compare the effectiveness of different network control strategies, like switching between different RATs, adjusting the RIS, and adapting the resource allocation strategy.

While experiment 1 provides the basis for both demos, experiment 2 contributes the main functionality for Demo 1 (cf. Section 5.1).

Table 7 provides a summary of experiment 2:

Table 7 PoC 1 summary of experiment 2 features.

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC1-EXP2</i>
Name	<i>Utilization of ML-DT in communications</i>

<p>Description</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Change in the industrial environment is emulated by inserting a mobile obstacle (wall). • The ML-DT updates the environment map by service request to DASH (requesting location information of obstacles). • The ML-DT updates the radio map based on the updated environment map. • The ML-DT adapts network parameters by <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Switching to another RAT (e.g. from 5G to Wi-Fi) ○ Adjusting RIS ○ Optimizing resource allocation to optimize different KPIs, for instance delay related KPIs (e.g. via xApp) • ML-DT re-evaluates network adaptations by updating the radio map after network parameter adaptation. • Validated network adaptation is applied to real network (e.g. via xApp).
<p>DASH Services (WP2)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Request location information of robots and (passive) moving obstacle
<p>MPS Technologies (WP3)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-static, multi-band, multi-technology sensing • Sensor fusion of raw data to obtain position information of AGV and moving obstacle.
<p>Targeted sensing / perception metrics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location information of passive obstacle (moving wall) • Location information of robots
<p>Targeted KPIs/KVIs (WP1)</p>	<p>KPI: Duration the communication service is not available [ms] KVI: Continuous connectivity of robots</p>
<p>Related Testbeds</p>	<p>5TONIC, STC Technikum</p>
<p>Targeted TRL (WP4)</p>	<p>TRL 3-4</p>

5.2.3 Experiment 3: Utilization of Multi-layer DT in Applications

Whereas experiment 2 focuses on the communication aspects, experiment 3 investigates how an ML-DT can support an industrial application. In this experiment, two robots jointly execute an intralogistics task, more specifically, robot B needs to deliver a workpiece to robot A in a changing environment. Jointly, here, means the robots have different sensing capabilities and they share their capabilities by means of an ML-DT.

Again, the change in the environment is emulated by introducing a mobile wall, which serves as a temporary obstacle. This change is detected by the ML-DT due to its environment and radio awareness capability (see experiment 1).

To manage these changes, the ML-DT continuously updates the environment map by issuing service requests to the DASH system, which supplies precise location information about obstacles. This ensures that the digital representation of the physical space remains accurate and current, reflecting any modifications such as the placement of the mobile wall. Besides the environmental mapping, the ML-DT also maintains the changes on the network coverage, which is crucial for communication-dependent operations. With this dual awareness – of both physical layout and network conditions – the ML-DT becomes a central coordinator for collaborative task execution. It evaluates the latest information and recalibrates the strategies of the robots accordingly.

For robot B, this means that its path planning needs to be dynamically adjusted. The ML-DT re-evaluates and updates the route of robot B based on the most recent data about obstacles and network connectivity. In practice, the adjusted path for robot B needs to consider two aspects: First, robot B cannot traverse the introduced wall, so the alternative path needs to circumvent that obstacle. Second, the alternative path should incorporate the radio map as well, to maintain network connectivity with sufficient performance for robot B during the execution of the intralogistics task. In addition, measures should be implemented to ensure that the dynamic path planning does not interfere with latency-sensitive control workloads.

To validate experiment 3 we aim to focus on the path planning adaptation delay, i.e. to evaluate the amount of time when a change in the environment has been triggered (e.g. wall being moved) until the AGV adapts its path accordingly. Here we aim to minimize the time robot B is in a blocking state w.r.t. navigation, in order to achieve a smooth navigation behaviour. That means, robot B is able to adapt its new trajectory on-the-fly.

Based on the foundational service from experiment 1, experiment 3 adds the main functionality for Demo 2 (see Section 5.1).

An overview of experiment 3 is summarized in Table 8:

Table 8 PoC 1 summary of experiment 3 features.

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC1-EXP3</i>
Name	<i>Utilization of Multi-layer DT in applications</i>
Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The robots provide their individual sensor data to the MPS. • Robot B relies on ISAC and external sensor data aggregated by the MPS. • Change in the industrial environment emulated by inserting a mobile wall (obstacle). • The ML-DT updates the environment map by service requests to DASH (location information of obstacles). • The ML-DT contains updated information on the environment and the network coverage. • The ML-DT coordinates the collaborative task execution of the robots by re-evaluating and updating the path planning for robot B, based on the current information on the environment and network coverage.
DASH Services (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Request location information of robots and (passive) moving obstacle</i>
MPS Technologies (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Multi-static, multi-band, multi-technology sensing</i> • <i>Sensor fusion of raw data to obtain position information of AGV and moving obstacle.</i>
Targeted sensing perception metrics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location information of passive obstacle (moving wall) • Location information of robots
Targeted KPIs/KVIs	<p>KPI: Amount of time, robot B is in a blocking state w.r.t. navigation adaptation [ms]</p> <p>KVI: Continuous/smooth navigation adaptation</p>

Related Testbeds (WP4)	STC Technikum
Targeted TRL (WP4)	TRL 3-4

5.2.4 Experiment 4: Operation of Multi-layer DT

At the core of the ML-DT is the layered organisation of the DTs. In this PoC, we focus on the following three DTs:

- DT of the environment.
- DT of the network.
- DT of the (industrial) application.

This experiment is on the operation of the ML-DT with a focus on its architectural design. This includes the testing of the interaction and seamless exchange of information across the DT layers. The integration of environmental, network, and application data facilitates more intelligent and context-aware decision-making. For instance, a change in network quality detected at the network layer can prompt adaptive navigation strategies at the application layer, while updated environmental conditions from sensor fusion can trigger reallocation of AGV tasks or modification of their planned trajectories.

Furthermore, we will evaluate the efficient interaction between the DTs and the real network components, such as the interaction with the MPS via the DASH, with the 5G or Wi-Fi controllers, as well as with the real application modules like path planning and/or task managers.

As this experiment is focusing on the operation and interaction between the different ML-DT layers and functionalities, it contributes to both demos (cf. Section 5.1). An overview of experiment 4 is summarized in Table 9:

Table 9 PoC1 summary of experiment 4

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC1-EXP4</i>
Name	<i>Operation of Multi-layer DT</i>

Description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real advantage of ML-DT is coming from the interaction and exchange of information between the various layers. • Efficient interaction with real network (e.g. 5G-/Wi-Fi-Controller) and with the real application (e.g. path planning/task manager).
DASH Services (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Request location information of robots and (passive) moving obstacle
MPS Technologies (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multi-static, multi-band, multi-technology sensing • Sensor fusion of raw data to obtain position information of AGV and moving obstacle.
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location information of passive obstacle (moving wall) • Location information of robots
Targeted KPIs/KVIs (WP1)	KVI: Correct parameter adaptation (DT <-> real world)
Related Testbeds (WP4)	STC Technikum
Targeted TRL (WP4)	TRL 3-4

5.3 Initial results

As one important part towards realization of PoC 1, we are going to validate the result obtained with the WP3 activities. The goal in WP3 is to obtain a site-specific SNR distribution estimation [18]. For the R&D of channel estimation methods, a link-level simulation with a realistic radio channel model is a key prerequisite. By means of a link-level simulator (e.g. Sionna by NVIDIA [19][20][21], we plan to use ray-tracing for a particular given digital representation of the environment in order to compute spatially consistent Channel Impulse Response (CIR), which statistical and stochastic models in network simulators cannot achieve [22][23]. In a first step, a scene file has to be created, which represents the environment DT, based on a 3D model of the environment. This 3D model composes the input of the Sionna ray-tracer. In the second step, Sionna is used to obtain the CIR from which the power delay and phase delay profile can be obtained. Using Gaussian Mixture Models (GMMs) we aim to use the CIR in order to obtain a Mixture of Gaussian (MoG) to approximate the SNR distribution and the envelope of a wireless channel propagating in the given factory environment [24][25]. By forming a grid of the underlying environment, the ray-tracer is going to compute the CIR for all the possible Tx-

Rx pairs in the grid. From the obtained SNR, a Block Error Rate (BLER) is obtained in the simulation, using a phy-abstraction model from Sionna or related work [26].

In a second step, the result is validated in a real testbed, using USRP devices [27]. By producing various numerical results for different scenario setups (moving vs. static objects, varying transmit power, location of the Tx-Rx pair, using RIS in the scenario, etc.) the obtained BLER and hence, SNR distribution can be validated and compared.

Furthermore, the PoC will be also used to assess the feasibility of some of the solutions proposed in WP2. In particular, the sensing information gathered within the DT will be exploited to improve the performance of radio resource management techniques. An illustrative example is, for instance, deploying a xApp that leverages sensing information to optimize the configuration of scheduling or resource allocation technique at physical resource level, which will be deployed at the gNB (DU) and in the DT. The behaviour of this solution will be assessed by means of delay-related KPIs.

6 PoC 2 Contact-free eHealth Monitoring at Home Environment

This PoC focuses on contact-free eHealth monitoring in the home environment, addressing one of the most pressing societal challenges: enabling unobtrusive, continuous, and privacy-preserving health monitoring for citizens. As healthcare systems face increasing pressure due to aging populations and rising demand, there is a strong need for solutions that can support early detection of health anomalies and long-term patient observation without imposing a burden on individuals or caregivers. Traditional approaches, such as wearable devices and camera-based systems, present limitations in terms of compliance, comfort, and privacy. Wearables require users to consistently wear and maintain the devices, which can be inconvenient and intrusive over time, while camera-based systems raise significant privacy concerns in domestic environments. In this context, PoC2 introduces a paradigm shift by leveraging the MultiX fusion Perceptive 6G-RAN (MP6R) and its ISAC capabilities to provide continuous monitoring of vital signs, such as respiration patterns and sleep quality, without requiring direct contact or invasive equipment.

This PoC demonstrates how the MP6R architecture supports seamless integration of sensing functions into the RAN and showcases a real-world application in the healthcare domain. Building on the technical foundations developed in WP2 and WP3, and on the integration activities of T4.1, the PoC validates the benefits of multi-static, multiband, and multi-technology fusion, which are enabled by MPS designs in WP3. By combining information from multiple distributed RAN nodes and heterogeneous sensing modalities, the system enhances robustness and accuracy, ensuring reliable performance in diverse home environments. Beyond the technical demonstration, PoC2 emphasizes data privacy and trustworthiness through the DASH, which provides secure aggregation, storage, and exposure of eHealth data. This ensures that sensitive personal information is managed in full compliance with ethical and regulatory frameworks, addressing one of the critical barriers to the adoption of eHealth solutions.

Overall, PoC2 positions contact-free eHealth monitoring as a flagship use case for 6G ISAC, fully aligned with 3GPP's vision for integrated sensing and the SNS JU roadmap. Its outcomes are expected to demonstrate the feasibility of deploying ISAC-enabled healthcare services in real-world home environments, while providing concrete insights that will inform standardization, interoperability, and market adoption. In this way, PoC2 not only validates the technical feasibility of contact-free health monitoring but also highlights the societal relevance, ethical responsibility, and industrial potential of ISAC in next-generation healthcare.

6.1 Targeted Demos

PoC2 consists of three demonstrations:

6.1.1 Demo 1: Human position and movements indicated by micro-Doppler spectrogram.

This demo showcases how the MP6R system can extract fine-grained information about human presence and motion by leveraging micro-Doppler signatures. By analysing the frequency shifts induced by human body movements (e.g., walking, limb motions), the system generates spectrograms that reveal both location and movement patterns in the monitored environment. The demonstration highlights the capability of ISAC-enabled RAN nodes to go beyond simple presence detection and to characterize human activity in a contact-free and privacy-preserving manner. This provides a foundation for applications such as fall detection, activity monitoring, and behavioural analysis in home healthcare scenarios. This demo corresponds to Experiment 1 in section 6.2.1.

6.1.2 Demo 2: Human breathing pattern estimated by visual and RF data augmentation.

This demo shows the ability of the MP6R system to monitor vital signs, with a focus on breathing patterns. Radio frequency signals are used to capture periodic chest movements, while visual sensing data are employed for validation and augmentation. The integration of RF and visual data enables robust estimation of respiration rate, even under challenging conditions such as non-line-of-sight or the presence of the moving interferer. The demonstration emphasizes the added value of multi-technology fusion, showing how combining RF sensing with auxiliary modalities can significantly improve accuracy and reliability. This capability is essential for contact-free health monitoring applications, particularly for sleep studies and continuous monitoring of respiratory conditions. This demo corresponds to Experiment 2 in section 6.2.2.

6.1.3 Demo 3: Gbps throughput and human location tracking.

This demo demonstrates the dual functionality of the MP6R system, combining high-throughput data communication with simultaneous human location tracking. Using advanced ISAC techniques, the system maintains gigabit-per-second connectivity while extracting location information of individuals in the environment. The demo highlights the ability of 6G RAN nodes to deliver both communication and sensing services without compromising performance, showcasing seamless integration of perception into the RAN. This dual capability is particularly relevant for future healthcare applications, where high-capacity data transfer (e.g., for medical imaging or real-time monitoring dashboards) can be combined with continuous user tracking to support safety and well-being in home environments. This demo corresponds to Experiment 3 in section 6.2.3.

6.2 Targeted experiments

6.2.1 Experiment 1: Human localization and motion estimation based on multi-band multi-static sensing

In the context of pervasive eHealth, the capability to continuously sense and interpret human 's activity without physical contact is a cornerstone for future 6G enabled healthcare services. Experiment 1 establishes the foundation of the PoC2 scenario by validating the use of multi-modal, multi-band ISAC sensing for the reliable detection, localization, and monitoring of human subjects in a home environment. The experiment demonstrates how the MultiX MPS and the Data Access and DASH cooperate to transform heterogeneous sensor data into actionable health-related information.

The experimental setup integrates distributed RUs operating at sub-6 GHz and mmWave frequencies together with auxiliary non-3GPP sensors, such as cameras and motion-capture systems. These heterogeneous sensing modalities generate complementary observations of the environment: the RF links capture micro-scale variations induced by chest movement or body motion, while visual and depth sensors provide macro-scale context on subject position and posture. The MPS aggregates and processes these data streams, executing fusion algorithms that combine spatial, temporal, and frequency-domain features to yield precise estimates of human position and motion.

Table 10 provides a summary of experiment 1.

Table 10 PoC 2 experiment 1 summary

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC2-EXP1</i>
Name	Human localization and motion estimation based on multi-band multi-static sensing
Description	In this experiment, the location of humans can be estimated by multi-static sensing schemes, which indicates that at least four distributed RUs are needed for a better localization accuracy, which is a Time of flight (ToF) based solution. In addition, using angle of arrival or departure (AoA and AoD) will be a complementary way, when a narrow beam is used at mmWave bands. We plan to collect channel state information data for people localization and tracking. In addition, the high-bandwidth USRP X410 is expected to be used for collecting channel data with higher delay resolution. Then, human limb motions will be demonstrated as micro-Doppler signatures, in which we will use motion capture systems to provide the ground truth by putting markers on different parts of human body.

DASH Services	<i>Data storage, data fusion, data training</i>
MPS Technologies	<i>Multi-static, multi-band, multi-technology sensing</i>
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy of localization of single human target. • Success rate of motion estimation accuracy
MultiX Innovations	Item related multi-static multi-band
Targeted KPIs/KVIs (WP1)	<i>KPI: localization error < 0.5 m, Velocity (Doppler) < 0.5 m/s</i> <i>KVI: Improve healthcare monitoring</i>
Benchmark	<i>We are targeting the KPIs defined in 3GPP TR 22.870</i>
Related Testbeds (WP4)	<i>PoC2-TB2 (Networked Systems Open Lab-mmWave testbed), PoC2-TB3 (Networked Systems Open Lab-mmWave testbed-6G Real-time Flexible Radio Access Network REF-RAN)</i>
Targeted TRL (WP4)	<i>TRL 3</i>

6.2.2 Experiment 2: Human vital sign estimation using RF and camera data augmentation

Vital sign estimation of human is challenging as the corresponding movements do not lead to the changes in the large-scale channel gain. However, these small movements can be detected when the test facilities are capable of sensing using bandwidth more than GHz level. Instead, vital signs also result in fluctuations in the phase of multipath components that can be reflections or scattering from human body. A key challenge to detect vital signs lie in the blockage and interference, which degrades the estimation performance if only a limited number of transceiver pairs are used. This experiment aims to demonstrate how we use distributed setup that includes multiple arrays in WP4 and signal processing framework defined in WP3 to achieve robust estimation of breathing patterns by leveraging spatial diversity and effective combination.

The realization of this experiment also aims at showcasing a set of the MultiX DASH capabilities that are well defined in WP2, namely: storage, fusion and exposure. The target is to showcase the exposure of the human vital sign estimation metrics to third party applications to trigger automated alarms upon detection of potential health issues (targeting mainly smart home scenarios). In this sense, the third-party application shall subscribe to the

specific sensing metric through the DASH exposure APIs to receive periodic reports and notifications of the targeted metric. Internally the MultiX MPS shall configure the sensing infrastructure, and the required data fusion processes to generate the requested metric.

An overview of experiment 2 is summarized in Table 11.

Table 11 PoC 2 experimental 2 summary

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC2-EXP2</i>
Name	Human vital sign estimation using RF and camera data augmentation
Description	To estimate the small-scale vibration of the human body, e.g., respiration, is challenging, even using the motion capture system. First of all, we will use the motion capture system to measure the breathing pattern by putting the markers on the human chest, not only on a static person (in this case, a good ground truth of breaths per minute (BPM) can be obtained). We will transfer the time-series data into the frequency domain, and then, through the frequency windowing, the BPM can be obtained. Multi-static radio channel data will be obtained in the same scenario.
DASH Services (WP2)	<i>Data storage, data fusion, data exposure</i>
MPS Technologies (WP3)	<i>Multi-static sensing algorithms</i>
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy of BPM estimation in frequency domain • Correlation level of breathing estimation and ground truth in time domain
MultiX Innovations (WP 5)	Item related multi-static
Targeted KPIs/KVIs (WP1)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>KPI: Correlation level > 85%, BPM error < 1 breath/min</i> • <i>KVI: Improve healthcare monitoring (indicated by % accuracy improvement for single/multiple antennas or centralized/distributed setup)</i>
Benchmark	<i>We are targeting the KPIs defined in ETSI ISG ISAC</i>

Related Testbeds (WP4)	<i>PoC2-TB1, Networked Systems Open Lab - Distributed Massive MIMO</i>
Targeted TRL (WP4)	TRL 3 - 4

6.2.3 Experiment 3: Integration of multi-gigabit communication with sensing-assisted presence detection

The realization of this experiment aims at showcasing a set of the MultiX DASH capabilities, namely: storage and exposure. The target is to showcase the exposure of object presence metrics to third-party applications to trigger automated alarms (likewise in Experiment 2). In this sense, the third-party application shall subscribe to the specific sensing metric through the DASH exposure APIs to receive periodic reports and notifications of the targeted metric. Internally the MultiX MPS shall configure the sensing infrastructure. Table 12 provides a summary of experiment 3.

Table 12 PoC 2 Experiment 3 summary

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC2-EXP3</i>
Name	Integration of multi-gigabit communication with sensing-assisted presence detection
Description	This experiment aims to test the potential of multi-Gigabit data transmission on top of the presence-detection capability of the advanced ISAC system developed in MultiX. With experiments 1 and 2, the accurate location will be given as input of this experiment to be used for precise beamforming. First, the Wi-Fi device will be used, based on the mmWave standards such as WiGig. The directional multi-gigabit (DMG) will be implemented in this experiment, benefiting from the wide bandwidth ranging from 57-66 GHz (unlicensed band). Then, the beam training and precoding will be conducted to make sure the beams from AP will directly point to the user equipment. Afterwards, the joint transmission using multiple APs will be tested in this experiment. Finally, the expected rate can achieve Gbps level, meantime, the human location is estimated in real time.
DASH Services (WP2)	<i>Sensing data storage, data exposure</i>

MPS Technologies (WP3)	<i>mmWave, ISAC efficiency</i>
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	Presence detection Communication throughput enhancement
MultiX Innovations (WP 5)	Items related presence detection, immersive connectivity
Targeted KPIs/KVIs	<i>KPIs: Probability of presence detection $\geq 95\%$, Peak communication data rate $\geq 1Gbps$ KVI: Improve healthcare monitoring</i>
Related Testbeds (WP4)	<i>PoC3-TB3, IHP - mmWave ISAC testbed</i>
Targeted TRL (WP4)	TRL 4

6.2.4 Experiment 4: Multi-sensor fusion for e-health applications of mobile robots.

Within the Contact-free e-health Monitoring at Home Environment PoC, this experiment integrates a mobile robot as a multi-sensor platform to enable domestic environment perception. This is done through the fusion of 3GPP signals and GNSS signals for localization, and through commercial e-health sensors. It complements the results of experiments 1-3, demonstrating an operative mobile platform capable of continuing the service provisioning even in scenarios with low coverage areas. The fusion and metric exposure are articulated through MPS and DASH, ensuring safe access to data and e-health related services.

The experiment considers (i) measuring and characterizing 3GPP and GNSS coverage, (ii) establishing baseline capabilities when only one of those technologies is available, (iii) moving between areas with different coverage conditions, evaluating the impact on localization accuracy and on the vital constant measurement capabilities, among others. The energy consumption will be evaluated as a key element of the viability of the experiment.

An overview of experiment 4 is summarized in Table 13.

Table 13 PoC2 experiment 4 summary

Item	Description
ID	<i>PoC2-EXP4</i>

Name	Multi-sensor fusion for e-health applications of mobile robots
Description	<p>Focus: Demonstration of the performance gains achievable when incorporating the ISAC-plus-available sensors fusion schema to domestic, indoors and outdoors e-health oriented mobile robots, and the viability of mobile-based vital signs measurement mobile platforms.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure coverage in different scenarios related to home environments, both indoor and outdoor (e.g., garden), for GPS and 5G using hardware loaded on the test robot. • Baseline establishment: test the robot using only 3GPP signals or only GNSS. • Move the robot between areas with different coverage levels and monitor localization accuracy. • Compare the performance of robotic functions (such as path planning, in-house fine navigation, assistance to e-health functions such as patient monitoring in no coverage areas, or periodic return to good coverage areas to relay recorded data) with and without our sensor fusion schema. • Evaluate the viability of vital signs measurement mounted on mobile platforms, employing commercial e-health sensors.
DASH Services (WP2)	<i>Access to location data of mobile measurement platform, data storage, data fusion</i>
MPS Technologies (WP3)	Multi-static, multi-technology sensing. Sensor fusion of raw data to obtain position information of mobile measurement platform.
Targeted sensing / perception metrics (WP3)	Location of mobile measurement platform , location of the patient.
MultiX Innovations	Improve robotic localization using 5G sensing and GNSS.
Targeted KPIs/KVIs	Mobile platform self-localization error < 0.5m
Related Testbeds	<i>Experiment deployed using i2CAT own infrastructure</i>

Targeted TRL (WP4)	TRL 3
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6.3 Initial results

This section reports on initial results obtained from initial software developments targeting PoC2 functionalities, including sensing enabler developments and system AI processing and fusion capabilities which will be further developed in the project for the realization of the PoC 2 experiments.

6.3.1 Contact-free respiration detection

This initial test aims to explore the signal processing techniques for massive MIMO-based respiration sensing, which is related to Experiment 2 in POC2. The RF data is collected from the Massive MIMO testbed at KU Leuven. The base station (BS) features a Baseband Unit (BBU) for high-PHY signal processing, 32 Software-Defined Radio (SDR) functioning as remote radio heads to handle low-PHY processing and a modular 64-antenna array, configured as 8 distributed uniform linear arrays with 8 antennas each. In this experiment, we rely on the UL channel estimation at the BBU. The single-antenna UE is also driven by an SDR connected to a host computer for signal processing. Tight synchronization between the user and the BS is achieved by connecting the local oscillators by a coax cable. The UL channel estimates are collected at a sample rate of 200 Hz. The testbed operates at a centre frequency of 3.51 GHz, with 100 subcarriers spanning an 18 MHz bandwidth with a subcarrier spacing of 180 KHz. The single-antenna UE employs an omnidirectional antenna for transmission, while the receiver antennas in the BS are patch antennas.

The ground truth is measured via Qualisys Miquis M3 Motion Capture cameras. This is a marker-based multi-camera motion capture system. The 3D motion capture data is collected at a sample rate of 150 Hz and is used as ground truth for the respiration estimation. The measurement is automated by simultaneously triggering the motion capture system and the Massive MIMO Testbed for data capture. This ensures time alignment between the 3D location data and the collected RF channels.

The BS's antenna arrays are positioned as depicted in Figure 26 and the subject is seated close to the UE. Four Mocap cameras were deployed to record ground truth data. We collected CSI from 10 subjects, consisting of 7 males and three 3 females, with 4 samples from each subject containing 1 minute of data each. To ensure data diversity, the UE was moved around each subject while keeping a close but varying distance, ranging from 0.5 m to 1.5 m. We gathered 40 CSI samples totalling 40 minutes of measurement. The dataset is available on IEEE Dataport [9]. Note that the consent form from the human subjects in the experiment has been obtained.

Figure 26 Measurement environment (left) and floorplan (right)

6.3.2 Multi-modal sensor fusion

Dynamic deep neural networks (DNNs) provide an adaptable framework for multi-sensor fusion, enabling intelligent and context-aware perception. Dynamic DNNs adjust in real time to shifting conditions, sensor dependability, and task demands, in contrast to static models. Adaptive input weighting, temporal alignment of asynchronous data, robustness against sensor failure, richer feature learning, and scalable integration of new modalities are some of the main advantages of Dynamic DNNs.

HydraFusion is a context-aware sensor fusion system designed for reliable object detection. It employs a split Faster R-Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with ResNet-18 and dynamically chooses early, late, or hybrid fusion techniques according to the context of the environment [8]. HydraFusion embodies key advantages of dynamic DNNs. The main components of HydraFusion model include stems which are sensor-specific feature extractors, fusion block where early fusion via concatenation and convolution is performed, branches where adaptive processing paths execute, gate modules where context-driven activation and routing are performed and late fusion where NMS for refined detection occurs. HydraFusion combines LiDAR, radar, and camera (L/R) data for effective, flexible inference [7].

This initial test is related to the Experiment 4 in PoC2.

As the first step, HydraFusion was trained and evaluated on two complementary datasets: Zenseact Open Dataset (ZOD) and RADIATE. These datasets offer diverse sensor modalities and environmental conditions, supporting robust generalization across driving scenarios which is explained in detail in Table 14. We remark that, although the datasets we have initially used refer to vehicular applications, the approach we developed applies to other sensor fusion domains as well and datasets that refer specifically to Experiment 4 in PoC2 are under consideration and the related results will be included in D4.2.

ZOD provides large-scale, high-resolution multimodal data collected across 14 European countries. Its structure—spanning independent frames, sequences, and full drives—supports

both short- and long-term learning. Timestamp-synchronized inputs from cameras, LiDAR, and radar enable reliable perception in structured urban and motorway environments.

RADIATE focuses on challenging weather conditions, offering synchronized data in fog, snow, rain, and night scenarios. It is especially useful for testing sensor fusion robustness when visual inputs are compromised [6].

Table 14 Multi-modal sensor fusion dataset summary and sensor modalities

Attribute	Zenseact Open Dataset (ZOD)	RADIATE Dataset
Camera	RGB (front-facing), 1024×512, anonymized	Stereo ZED, 672×376 @15FPS, weatherproof
LiDAR	Temporal scans (±1s), 10Hz, fused history	Velodyne HDL-32e, 360°, 10Hz, 32-channel
Radar	ARS513, 60ms interval, 102–250m, adaptive modes	Navtech CTS350-X, 100m, 1.8° resolution, 360° azimuth
GPS/IMU	OXTS, timestamp-synced, high-precision	Advanced Navigation, robust in all conditions
Annotations	2D/3D boxes, lane polygons	2D/3D boxes, drivable areas
Focus	Urban/motorway environments	Adverse weather scenarios
Fusion Strengths	Semantic depth + geometric precision	Visual robustness + sensor complementarity

Model Training Procedure. HydraFusion model was trained using a custom PyTorch pipeline optimized for multi-modal input. The training setup enabled efficient processing of heterogeneous sensor data, ensuring scalability and robustness across diverse datasets. Table 15 presents the training configuration parameters.

Table 15 FL Training configuration

Parameter	Value
Activation	ReLU
Learning Rate	1×10^{-4}
Batch Size	1
Epochs	50 (per client round)
Device	CUDA-enabled GPU

Given the high-dimensional and multi-modal nature of the fused sensor inputs, these parameters were chosen to strike a balance between model convergence and stability. Normalized camera pictures (C×H×W), LiDAR-derived BEV tensors, radar feature maps, 2D/3D bounding box annotations, and sensor calibration matrices were all included in pre-processed .pkl files that were loaded during training. The HydraFusion architecture processed these inputs for improved object detection and modality-specific training.

Model Inference Procedure. HydraFusion performs inference in evaluation mode with gradients disabled, using a custom PyTorch pipeline. Predictions are generated from the fused output layer and visualized using Matplotlib. An Intersection-over-Union (IoU) threshold of 0.4 was applied to filter high-confidence detections. Additional post-processing steps such as skip-box filtering and temporal smoothing were used to refine detection quality.

Results. Prediction accuracy was assessed across object classes using various sensor configurations. Table 16 summarizes performance for single sensors, pairwise combinations, and full multi-modal fusion.

Table 16 Sensor-wise Prediction Accuracy (%)

Sensors	Car	Van	Truck	Trailer	Snow Marker	Position	Speed
Camera (Cam)	13.30	23.08	16.67	11.00	6.25	17.50	12.37
Radar	40.00	41.44	49.00	6.25	7.69	56.25	27.00
LiDAR	35.71	15.38	16.67	8.00	28.57	31.26	19.96
Camera (Both)	13.40	23.20	20.04	11.76	6.25	18.00	12.40
Radar + LiDAR	47.34	28.57	25.10	40.00	53.33	34.38	26.42
LiDAR + Camera	18.75	14.29	25.00	33.33	20.00	18.80	17.50
HydraFu sion	76.67	66.67	70.00	92.80	78.57	61.88	66.58

Initial results with the HydraFusion model, evaluated on autonomous vehicle datasets Zenseact Open Dataset (ZOD) and RADIATE, demonstrate its capability to enhance robustness under challenging conditions. The model shows strong performance across diverse environments, including adverse weather and low-visibility scenarios, confirming the effectiveness of sensor fusion for reliable detection.

Alongside accuracy, prediction outputs of Initial results were scaled back to the original image resolution for visualization. Green bounding boxes denote ground truth while red boxes represent HydraFusion predictions. Figure 27 showcases HydraFusion output on the RADIATE and Zenseact Open Dataset (ZOD).

Figure 27: HydraFusion prediction (Red) and ground truth (Green) visualized on the Radiate and ZOD Dataset

Originally designed for multi-modal perception in autonomous vehicles, as explained in previous sections, HydraFusion models architecture, which selectively blends sensor outputs according to environmental reliability, can adapt to a wide range of complex scenarios.

RF-based respiration monitoring with BS-Breath dataset includes ground truth respiration data from a Motion Capture device and RF channel measurements from a 64-antenna massive MIMO testbed. Implementing HydraFusion for RF-based respiration monitoring with the BS-Breath dataset is a notable extension [10].

The suggested adaptation entails transforming unstructured radio frequency signals into image representations that are compatible with HydraFusion's input formats, like heatmaps or spectrograms. The gating and fusion modules will be modified to include RF features in addition to conventional sensor data, and a separate RF processing branch will be introduced.

The objective is to create a reliable respiration estimate system that can forecast waveform patterns, confidence scores, and breathing rate (BPM) while being compared to Motion Capture ground truth. In addition to expanding HydraFusion's use beyond autonomous systems, this innovation creates new opportunities for non-invasive health monitoring in dynamic settings.

6.3.3 Movement-Robust mmWave VR via Dual-Beam Reception for multi-gigabit communication

This initial test explores the feasibility of robust multi-gigabit communication for Virtual Reality (VR) applications in highly dynamic user scenarios, using KU Leuven’s mmWave testbed operating at 60 GHz. This initial test is related to the Experiment 3 in PoC2. The platform integrates coordinated multi-point access with dual-beam reception at the head-mounted display (HMD), ensuring continuous connectivity despite rapid head movements. By leveraging widely separated access points (APs) together with steerable antenna subarrays on the HMD, the setup extends angular coverage and minimizes service outages caused by beam misalignment.

The KU Leuven testbed combines an RFSoc ZCU111 baseband platform with Pharrowtech 60 GHz RF front-ends, supporting programmable beam codebooks and hybrid beamforming. This enables the evaluation of multi-gigabit VR streaming performance under realistic motion traces, using datasets of six-degrees-of-freedom (6DoF) HMD movements. In the experiment, two APs are positioned at different angles around the test area, and the HMD emulator is equipped with two steerable antenna subarrays, as shown in Figure 28. Both the APs and the HMD are configured with programmable beam codebooks. During the test, the HMD maintains two active beams simultaneously, each connected to a different AP or subarray, so that when one beam degrades due to movement or blockage, the other continues to sustain the communication link. Motion traces are then replayed to emulate natural VR head dynamics, producing rapid rotations and orientation changes that stress-test the system. Multi-gigabit VR traffic streams are transmitted over the 60 GHz links, and the system performance is assessed in terms of throughput stability, link outage probability, and transition smoothness. By comparing dual-beam reception against a single-beam baseline, the experiment highlights the improved angular coverage and robustness of the platform in maintaining uninterrupted high-rate VR experiences [11].

This test contributes to Experiment 3 by showcasing the communication platform capabilities required for joint multi-gigabit transmission and user-awareness. It complements broader objectives of the project by demonstrating how multi-antenna and multi-point coordination can be deployed in practice to achieve robust high-throughput connectivity. The results are reported in Table 17

(a) Dual-connectivity VR setup

(b) Measurement layout

Figure 28 Dual-AP measurement setup

Table 17 Initial PoC 2 experiment 3 results

Inadequate understanding of informed consent by participants	Medium	Medium	Provide accessible, clear consent forms. Staff to explain the study thoroughly.	Repeat consent process if participant feedback shows confusion.
Misinterpretation of health data leading to false conclusions	Low	High	Collaborate with healthcare professionals to validate data interpretation.	Introduce human review of health conclusions.
Discomfort or privacy concerns due to passive sensing technologies	Low	Medium	Conduct a risk assessment and respect participants' privacy and comfort during real-time monitoring.	Establish a clear complaint procedure and resolve issues within 30 days.

7 Ethics compliance

All activities described in this deliverable have been developed in full alignment with the ethical framework and procedures established in *Deliverable D7.1 – Ethics Requirements and Procedures*. Although *D4.1* focuses exclusively on defining the integration and validation methodology and describing the MultiX Open Labs, and therefore does not involve any experimental activity with human participants or personal data collection, ethics has been carefully considered throughout the methodological design to ensure full compliance once the experiments are executed.

The ethical framework defined in *D7.1* has guided the definition of the Open Labs and validation methodology. The appointed *Ethics Advisor* (EA) has reviewed the procedures to ensure their conformity with the applicable EU and national legal frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR 2016/679) and the Horizon Europe ethical standards. Each partner hosting an Open Lab has confirmed compliance with institutional and national ethics requirements, as well as the principles of the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity.

While this deliverable does not report experimental results, some of the planned Proofs of Concept (in particular PoC 2, *Contact-free eHealth Monitoring at Home Environment*) will involve controlled experiments with human participants. The ethical implications of such activities have already been analysed in *D7.1*. Specifically, PoC 2 will rely on non-invasive sensing technologies (RF and camera-based) and will involve voluntary participants—initially PhD student volunteers—under explicit informed consent. All related procedures, including participant information, consent collection, and data protection mechanisms, have been approved as part of the ethics compliance verification carried out under WP7. No experimentation involving vulnerable individuals or health-related data will take place without prior review and authorization by the EA and relevant institutional ethics committees.

The Open Lab methodology integrates privacy and data protection considerations from the outset. The architecture and data flows described in this document have been designed following the GDPR principles of purpose limitation, data minimization, and security. Where future experiments involve personal data, Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) will be performed in accordance with the procedure already established in *D7.1*. Data will be pseudonymized, securely stored, and accessible only to authorized researchers.

Ethical compliance has been embedded as a methodological requirement in the integration and validation workflow. The experiment and test templates defined in this deliverable include explicit references to ethics compliance and data protection steps, ensuring that each experiment conducted within the MultiX Open Labs will automatically adhere to the established ethical and legal procedures. This guarantees that all future PoC activities will be conducted responsibly, transparently, and in full alignment with the ethical standards of the MultiX project.

8 Conclusions

In conclusion, the experimental, integration, and validation framework presented in this document provides a solid foundation for the successful realization and assessment of the MultiX project's technological innovations. By defining a structured yet flexible methodology, the framework ensures a coherent approach to integrating the diverse software components within the MultiX ecosystem. The integration with the MultiX Open Labs and test environments not only enables systematic experimentation but also establishes traceability mechanisms to monitor progress and evaluate outcomes against the established objectives, in terms of targeted demonstrations and TRL levels, software components and technologies validated. This methodological rigor guarantees that the validation process remains aligned with the overall project milestones and objectives.

Moreover, the combination of the MultiX Open Labs, the MPS, the MP6RC, and the DASH creates an experimental infrastructure capable of supporting advanced PoC demonstrations. The conducted PoC experiments effectively illustrate the potential of MultiX technologies in enabling ISAC across multi-technology and multi-band environments. Through targeted vertical scenarios, the project has validated key innovations such as enhanced sensor fusion, automated configuration, and exposure of sensing results. Overall, the framework and experimental activities have demonstrated the maturity and applicability of MultiX solutions, paving the way for their adoption in future intelligent network deployments and real-world vertical scenarios and use cases.

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